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Administrative social science data discoverability

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The Social Science Research Infrastructure Network acknowledges the Traditional Owners and their custodianship of the lands on which we work. We pay our respects to their Ancestors and their descendants, who continue cultural and spiritual connections to Country.

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Executive Summary

Australia's social science research landscape is increasingly shaped by the availability of large-scale administrative data generated through government service delivery and record-keeping systems. With whole-of-population data spanning domains such as health, education, welfare, employment, and housing, among others, these data assets offer powerful opportunities for social scientists to conduct policy-relevant research. At the same time, these data assets can be uniquely challenging for researchers to understand, particularly at the earliest stages of the research lifecycle. In this initial discovery phase, where social scientists identify, locate, and assess the suitability of relevant datasets, the lack of clear and discoverable metadata creates barriers to efficient research. This report and its resulting metadata catalogue address a widely-acknowledged gap in Australia's social science research infrastructure: the limited discoverability of administrative social science data and the absence of a data discovery tool centred on the needs of social science researchers.

The report has two complementary components. Part 1 (Environmental Scan Report) documents the current landscape of Australian administrative social science data and presents the development and results of a structured metadata catalogue designed to support early data discovery. Part 2 (Technical Solutions Report) explores and assesses options for transforming the static administrative metadata catalogue into a web-based discovery tool, tailored to the needs of social science researchers.

Environmental Scan of Australian Administrative Data

Administrative data relevant to social policy domains and social scientific research are often difficult to find and inconsistently documented, requiring pre-existing or insider knowledge to fully understand. While numerous open data portals exist (e.g., data.gov.au) which focus on a variety of types of data, metadata for restricted, unit-record administrative datasets tend to be fragmented across multiple sources or inaccessible without prior approvals. Consequently, researchers have a limited ability to discover and assess the feasibility of conducting research with a given administrative data source.

To address this, the SSRIN undertook an environmental scan of Australian administrative data assets relevant to social science research, with a specific focus on early-stage data discovery. A review of features and metadata field structures used in existing Australian data discovery tools revealed common inclusions and gaps, particularly in relation to purpose of data collection, population scope, methods of compilation, and high-level statements about data quality and limitations. Based on these findings and consultations with the SSRIN User Reference Group of social science researchers and data professionals, the team designed a metadata field structure optimised for early-stage discovery of administrative datasets. The fields prioritise information critical for initial relevance assessment, including purpose, topical coverage, population scope, units of observation, temporal and geographic coverage, access pathways, and known data quality issues.

Using defined inclusion criteria and a multi-pronged search strategy, the environmental scan identified and documented 97 administrative data assets, comprising 80 stand-alone datasets and 17 integrated data assets which contain multiple datasets linked together. The resulting HTML metadata catalogue reveals a data landscape heavily concentrated in health, education, and employment-related domains. Most of the administrative datasets are national in scope and updated annually. Importantly, more than half of the stand-alone datasets are components of one or more integrated data assets, underscoring the growing prominence of linkage infrastructures in Australian social science research and showing the need for a data discoverability tool that allows users to understand how different administrative datasets relate to one another.

Despite the breadth of available data, discoverability is harmed by incomplete, inconsistently named, or outdated metadata. For instance, relationships between related data assets (e.g., several distinct datasets

derived from a common data collection or warehouse) or renamed data collections can be poorly documented. Over time, custodianship can change, integrated assets can evolve their holdings, and documentation and measurement practices can vary, further exacerbating confusion for researchers unfamiliar with a given data source. As a result, many administrative data assets remain effectively hidden from researchers during the crucial scoping and design phases of research.

Scoping Technical Pathways to an Interactive Discoverability Tool

While creating a static metadata catalogue provided a first step to documenting administrative data assets relevant for Australian social scientific research, Part 2 explores how the SSRIN metadata catalogue could be transformed into an interactive data discoverability tool.

Drawing on a scan of existing discovery platforms, consultations with social science researchers, and discussions with technical experts, Part 2 identifies core user needs that are not adequately met by current tools. Researchers emphasised the need for nuanced and conceptually meaningful search and filtering mechanisms and consistency in metadata across entries. Technical consultations suggested open-source data management systems as platforms that balance efficiency while providing robust search, filtering, metadata customisation, and API capabilities. Hosting via the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud was recommended as a cost-effective and strategically aligned option.

Key user experience features include faceted search aligned with early discovery needs, consistent, well-defined metadata fields supported by controlled vocabularies when possible, stable URLs for citation and sharing, and mechanisms for saving, exporting, and comparing discovery results. Equally important is the design of the back-end infrastructure, including customisation of the metadata field structure, validation rules, automation for link checking and metadata ageing, and clear workflows to maintain quality and consistency over time.

The report provides indicative estimates of technical and staffing requirements. Building the tool would require approximately six months of full-time development effort using an existing platform, while ongoing technical maintenance would be relatively modest. Content maintenance and updating to prevent the metadata catalogue from becoming outdated would also require sustained involvement from social scientists with domain expertise. Long-term success therefore depends not only on technical implementation, but also on governance arrangements, institutional commitment, and partnerships and communication with data custodians.

Conclusion

Australia possesses a rich and growing, yet fragmented, ecosystem of unit-record level administrative data assets of interest to social scientists. A key barrier, however, is their limited discoverability and inconsistent documentation. The SSRIN metadata catalogue addresses this gap by consolidating high-level metadata across key domains in a researcher-friendly format. Transforming this catalogue into an interactive discovery tool represents a feasible, high-impact investment that would substantially increase data discoverability and reduce barriers to using administrative data for research, thereby strengthening Australian social science research infrastructure.

Introduction

Australia's social science research landscape is entering a period of transformation, underpinned by the rapid expansion of digital records and the increasing availability of new forms of administrative data. Whereas earlier researchers relied primarily on censuses and surveys, today they can access a broader range of resources such as large administrative datasets, tax and health records etc. generated through everyday interactions with public services. These developments present unique opportunities to understand social, economic, and health dynamics with greater precision, timeliness, and scale than ever before.

At the same time, this transformation also raises critical questions about equity, access, and the long-term sustainability of research infrastructure. Without careful investment and governance, there is a risk that data systems will entrench existing gaps, privilege certain research agendas, or exclude marginalised communities. The *Decadal Plan for the Social Sciences in Australia*, developed by the Academy of the Social Sciences in Australia (2024), acknowledges this transformation. It emphasises the need for sustained investment in data infrastructure, stronger interoperability standards, improved digital research skills, and robust governance frameworks. The Plan identifies integrated data systems as essential tools to respond to Australia's most urgent social, economic, and environmental challenges. Together with the *National Research Infrastructure Roadmap (2021)* and the *Data-Enabled Research Future report (2022)*, the Plan emphasises that the capacity of the social sciences to address complex issues now depends on the strength of national data infrastructure.

Three emerging strategic directions include:

1. Digitally-enabled and integrated data infrastructure, to expand access to harmonised, linked datasets across domains such as health, education, housing, employment, and social services
2. Advanced methodological capabilities, to enable social scientists to harness computational and interdisciplinary approaches while maintaining the integrity of interpretive and qualitative methods
3. Coordinated and ethical infrastructure governance, to support inclusivity, transparency, Indigenous Data Governance, and culturally appropriate data use.

Taken together, these strategic directions create the foundations for a stronger data ecosystem.

Administrative data relevant to social science and social policy domains¹ play a central role in this vision, serving both as a practical expression of these priorities and as the mechanism through which they can be achieved. However, a key challenge for researchers is that administrative data and even its associated metadata is often not findable or accessible, ultimately reducing its use in social science research. Improved discoverability and clear access pathways are preconditions for rigorous, cumulative research because they shorten time-to-analysis and make comparative designs feasible across portfolios (Leigh, 2023).

Aims of this report

This report forms part of the Social Science Research Infrastructure Network (SSRIN), an initiative to strengthen Australia's social science research capability by developing accessible and sustainable research infrastructure. One of SSRIN's activity streams focuses on data discovery and access, aiming to improve how social scientists locate and assess data assets for potential research use, with a particular emphasis on administrative datasets. This activity stream targets some of the practical barriers that prevent researchers

¹ References to "administrative data" largely refer to unit-record level data with information relevant to social policy and social scientific topical domains in line with inclusion criteria specified in Part 1 of this report rather than the entire universe of administrative data.

from fully capitalising on the available data, thereby enhancing the 'FAIR'-ness of such data assets (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

Data discoverability—particularly of administrative datasets—was identified during a co-design process undertaken by the Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences and Indigenous Australian Research Data Commons (HASS+I ARDC) as a major, cross-cutting gap in the Australian social science data landscape that limits researchers' ability to capitalise on available data assets. This aligns with broader sectoral analyses, including the *Academy's Decadal Plan*, which emphasise the need for coordinated discovery services and high-quality metadata to unlock the value of existing data.

To that end, Part 1 of this report describes how a metadata catalogue intended to support early assessments of research suitability of administrative data assets was created. While this catalogue, included as separate attachments, offers a static and partial picture of the administrative social science data landscape in Australia, it represents an important first step in enhancing data discoverability for administrative data assets. The outlined inclusion criteria and search strategy attempt to structure the collection of metadata for administrative data assets which may be of particular interest to social scientists. Likewise, metadata are intended to present readers with important elements consistently, such as the purpose of each data collection, their units of observation, and scope, among others, which are invaluable for determining the potential uses of a new dataset. Cataloguing these metadata for administrative data assets in a single resource also reduces the time it takes researchers to discover and evaluate new data sources. As such, three goals of this report are to (1.) document a process by which metadata may be collected and catalogued for administrative data assets (Part 1 of this report), (2.) provide a centralised catalogue of administrative data assets with information useful for social science researchers interested in using Australian administrative data (Attachments 1 and 2), and (3.) outline technical and practical specifications that would allow the creation of an interactive, web-based discoverability tool that incorporates content from the catalogue of administrative data metadata (Part 2 of this report).

Based on the above, this report proposes a practical pathway to address the discoverability gap and to enable consistent and efficient use of priority administrative datasets. It proceeds with a discussion of some advantages and limitations of administrative data for social science research, then describes inclusion and exclusion criteria and the search strategy, as well as a list of metadata fields to be populated. It subsequently summarises results of the environmental scan and offers observations about the discoverability of administrative data surfaced during the process of the scan. Results of the Environmental Scan, available as separate html documents (Attachments 1 and 2), collate metadata of Australian administrative data resources in a novel, user friendly format for researchers. These attachments include metadata vital for researchers trying to locate and understand how existing administrative data sources may be suitable for their proposed research questions.

In Part 2 of this document, technical specifications are detailed which show how the metadata catalogue from the Environmental Scan may be converted into a searchable, filterable tool for early data discovery, as well as potential constraints and resource requirements for the ongoing technical and content maintenance of such a resource.

Part 1

Environmental Scan Report

1. Environmental Scan Report

1.1 Administrative Data Relevant to Social Science and Policy Domains

Administrative data are a particularly important resource which can be used to enhance social science research. The Australian Bureau of Statistics defines administrative data as information that government departments, businesses and other organisations collect for reasons other than research, such as registrations, billing and record keeping. Administrative data most relevant for social scientific research can include information from domains such as education, welfare, justice, health, housing, or other social policy domains. These data are drawn from sources such as government service records, tax filings, health registries, and welfare systems, and are curated for statistical and research purposes. In practice, these administrative data sources represent a harmonised evidence base that enables longitudinal, cross-sectoral, and policy-relevant analysis of Australian society.

1.1.1 Advantages of administrative data

Comprehensive coverage

Data held in administrative records (such as health, tax, welfare, and education data) cover entire populations or very large cohorts. This provides researchers with near-universal coverage of Australian individuals, households, and communities, minimising the sampling error inherent in survey-based studies.

Longitudinal insights

Administrative data are longitudinal by design. This supports the study of life-course outcomes, intergenerational patterns, and the long-term impacts of policy interventions. These areas are difficult to capture through cross-sectional surveys alone.

Policy relevance

Government administrative data is directly tied to government service delivery, making it highly relevant for evaluating policies and programs. It enables evidence-based assessment of reforms in areas such as health care, education, housing, and labour markets, ensuring that social science research directly informs policy decisions.

Reduced respondent burden and bias

Administrative data are collected in the course of service delivery, which means researchers do not need to rely on large-scale surveys for every project. This reduces respondent burden and helps avoid recall bias and self-reporting inaccuracies, leading to more reliable measures of behaviours and outcomes.

Linkage across different domains

Administrative data enables the linkage of data across different areas, for example, connecting education, health, employment, and justice datasets. This multidimensional perspective allows researchers to examine complex, interconnected social problems.

Equity and inclusion

Administrative data often includes detailed demographic information (age, sex, Indigenous status, geography, etc.), enabling equity-focused analyses of disadvantaged or marginalised groups. This provides opportunities to study characteristics that are rare in the population, for example, certain medical conditions

or long-term follow-ups of high-risk cohorts. It supports research into disparities in health, education, income, and service access.

1.1.2 Limitations of administrative data

Despite their many advantages, the use of administrative data presents significant methodological and practical challenges. Four issues are particularly important.

Purpose and scope of administrative data

Administrative data are collected for operational, not research, purposes. This may cause inconsistencies in coding, changes in definitions, and variations across jurisdictions that complicate longitudinal comparability. Importantly, researchers have no (or very limited) control over the content of the data, which in practice limits the scope of the available data to what is collected by the respective agencies for the purpose of service delivery. Unlike longitudinal surveys, there is no scope for researchers to ask tailored questions. Furthermore, administrative data is limited to capturing people's characteristics and behaviours but does not capture reasons behind these behaviours, attitudes, beliefs, or subjective perceptions.

Statistical limitations

There are some statistical drawbacks such as linkage bias, where incomplete or inaccurate matching across datasets may produce skewed findings. Missing values, unrepresentative populations, and limited researcher control over content can further complicate analysis. A further limitation is that data collected through administrative systems often reflect the assumptions, values, and historical norms of the dominant culture, and may be shaped by government priorities regarding what information is deemed important. As a result, such data may fail to adequately reflect the diversity of lived experiences within the population (Milne et al., 2022). For instance, health datasets have historically under-represented Indigenous health concepts, meaning that important aspects of community health are excluded from administrative records (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, 2025).

Privacy and confidentiality

Combining multiple anonymised datasets can inadvertently re-identify individuals, which poses risks to confidentiality. To address these risks, individual-level administrative social science datasets often have heavy restrictions in place upon their access, including requirement to work in a secure environment. While these protections are vital, they can limit transparency and hinder replication.

Restrictive conditions of use

Access to administrative data is subject to relatively complex application processes, project-specific approvals, and ongoing compliance requirements, especially for unit record data. Researchers must often work within secure laboratory environments with limited export rights, which can lengthen project timelines and reduce flexibility. These conditions reduce the openness of administrative data assets.

Limited metadata

Metadata describing the content, coverage, and quality of administrative data are frequently incomplete or inconsistently documented. This lack of documentation makes it difficult for researchers to fully understand data origin, governance, and processing or compare datasets across time and jurisdictions.

Together, the advantages and challenges of administrative data underline both their transformative potential and their practical limitations. While administrative data provide unique opportunities for comprehensive, longitudinal, and policy-relevant research, restrictive access conditions, limited metadata, and operational inconsistencies mean that their effective use depends heavily on robust governance and researcher expertise. Therefore, it is critical to examine the current landscape of administrative data in Australia to understand what resources already exist, how they are being applied, and where gaps remain. The following

section outlines the methodological framework employed to examine the contemporary landscape of administrative social sciences datasets in Australia. It identifies the strategies adopted for systematic description and structured searches and provide results of an environmental scan of some key administrative data assets.

1.2 Approach

This study employed a two-phase approach to generate a catalogue with information about administrative data. In Phase 1, the research team developed a template which contained key metadata fields relevant to important data discovery needs of researchers. This process was undertaken in three steps. First, the team defined early data discovery needs conceptually. The team then investigated how metadata field structures used in existing online data discovery tools have addressed early data discovery needs of social researchers. To this end, the team undertook a scan of data discovery tools with the capability to discover administrative datasets in the Australian context.

After that the team drafted a metadata field structure by identifying alignment and gaps between metadata field structures that currently exist in prominent data discovery tools and early data discovery information needs of social researchers. The metadata field structure was then tested and confirmed with users.

In Phase 2 the research team defined and executed a (meta)data search and population strategy for generating a catalogue of administrative data assets. This included defining criteria for data in scope of the catalogue and a search process for identifying data in scope.

1.2.1 Development of metadata field structure for data catalogue

1.2.1.1 Metadata needs and early data discovery

Social researchers can have various information needs related to data; however, there are some common needs related to an early data discovery stage. Catalogues that present information on data assets need to consider what aspects of a data asset they should display, and to which level of detail. A data catalogue, such as the one created during this project, is meant to facilitate the discovery of many data assets to users who have no familiarity with them at all. What the catalogue then should enable is called here ‘early data discovery’, which is distinct from other stages of data discovery researchers can be interested in. To draw out these distinctions, data discovery stages and associated information needs are conceptualised in Table 1.

Questions in early data discovery are of this kind: ‘What kind of data exist?’, ‘What can the data potentially be used for?’ and ‘Are the data potentially useful for my research interest?’ Early data discovery needs are distinguished here from later data discovery needs that are concerned with questions (see Key questions column in Table 1) that become relevant as researchers approach using the data – questions that escalate from ‘potentially’ using the data to ‘actually’ using the data. Answering these questions can require very detailed information on the data content, information on data access protocols and associated time frames, data structures and file formats as outlined in the *Primary information needs* column in the table.

The early data discovery needs are synonymous with the user journey Stage 1 in the table. The primary information needs at this stage relate to developing a general understanding of the capabilities of the data, which can be gained by addressing these questions:

- What was the original collection/compilation designed to do?
- How was the data collected/compiled?
- What is the content of the data?

- What are the capabilities/limitations as defined by others?
- In which forms can the data be accessed and where can one get further information?

These questions could be answered at different levels of detail. For example, questions on the content of a data asset could go down to providing detailed variable level documentation that shows distributions of values and how a variable or field changed over time as is not uncommon in administrative data collections of a longitudinal nature. Similarly, data limitations could be outlined at the level of individual cases or variables leading to detailed and long documentation. Gaining such detailed understanding of the data is relevant for assessing the capability of the data for specific research interests. However, in the data discovery journey the need to gain such understanding often comes later. For early data discovery general responses to the first four questions are sufficient, when complemented by a clear path to gain further information if early data discovery has led to interest in a particular data asset. A data catalogue that combines relatively high-level information across multiple data assets is an adequate tool for early discovery.

In the following model (Table 1) the information needs for later data discovery stages (2 to 6) are considered as secondary for early data discovery.

Table 1. Stages of data discovery and primary information needs for researchers

Research analyst user journey	Key questions	Primary information needs for researchers
Stage 1. Identifying potential relevance of data for research interest	What data exist? What can the data potentially be used for? Are the data potentially useful for my research interest?	Understanding: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how the data asset can be identified • what the underlying collection was designed to do • the method and scope of collection/compilation (how collected/compiled, unit of observation, sample/population/coverage, geography, timeframes) • data content (concepts, topics, variables) • broad capabilities and limitations of data • what data may be accessible • where to get further information about data and data access
Stage 2. Ascertaining suitability of data for research purpose	Are the data suitable for a given research question? What level of certainty is there that the data can be used to answer the research question? Do the features of the data ensure pursuing my research interest?	Understanding: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • more details of context (legal foundations; agencies involved) • details of micro-data (variable values, missing values, changes to variables, who supplied what when) • distributions of values (frequency and summary stats)

- more detailed limitations of data (systematic and random errors in data entry/processing– changes in context affecting data, data integration and coverage, accuracy and coherency also related to subgroups and/or individual variables)
- more detailed provenance (original data entry forms, questions, data entry guidelines and protocols, derivation rules, data cleaning, quality assurance, weighting, retrospective edits, data integration [selections, transformations, linkage, editing etc.]

Stage 3.
Assessing
feasibility

Is it **practically feasible** that working with the data ensures pursuing my research interest given my timelines, resourcing and capabilities?

Understanding:

- data access protocols (eligibility, required training, timeframes, costs)
- technical hardware and software requirements
- data use protocols (including associated user limitations and disclosure processes including timelines, if applicable)

Stage 4.
Working with the
data I

How do I **read in, link (if applicable), format, clean, and label** the data?

Understanding:

- data file structures, sizes and formats
- how to read in, label, transform, link etc data
- how to access help

Stage 5.
Working with the
data II

How do I **analyse** the data in a way that addresses the features of the data (quality)?

Understanding:

- data as under Stage 2
- relevant and appropriate data analysis procedures that take account of data quality
- how to access help

Stage 6.
Working with the
data III

How do I **report** the results **adequately**?

Understanding:

- how to interpret results and with what disclaimers
- how to quote and reference the data asset in publications

Notes: The table conceptualises information needs about data (metadata) including accessing data from a researcher's point of view. It does not consider data management tools, such as scripts that can execute certain procedures as metadata. It does also not explicitly consider information needs related to metadata itself, such as metadata version, update cycle and associated administrative control. Source: adjusted from Kubler et al. 2024, p26.

1.2.1.2 Metadata field structures in existing tools that discover administrative data

1.2.1.2.1 Process

Having conceptualised information needs for researchers in early data discovery processes, we undertook a scan of existing online data discovery tools for administrative data that have prominence in the Australian context to assess in which way these tools accounted for these (and other) information needs in their metadata field structures. These data discovery tools² were identified through targeted online searches and the research team's existing knowledge of national research infrastructure. They included online data search functions offered by:

- The Australian Data Archive (ADA Dataverse),
- The Australian Government (Dataplace),
- The Population Health Research Network (PHRN),
- The Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network (AURIN),
- The Australian Research Data Commons (Research Data Australia), and
- The National Housing Data Exchange Platform (NDHE).

ADA Dataverse specialises in national surveys in social science domains, such as the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics (HILDA) survey and the ANU Poll. Dataplace holds information for many data assets across disciplinary fields with most of the data assets falling outside the scope of social science data. Compared to ADA it offers discovery of more Government administrative data.

PHRN (Public Health Research Network) supports health and human services research by facilitating secure access to linked administrative and health datasets across Australian jurisdictions. It administers a metadata registry for data assets held by data linkage units and custodians, helping researchers identify available datasets and understand their structure, content, and linkage potential. AURIN (Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network) focuses on spatially-enabled urban and socio-economic data with an interactive GIS-based interface tailored for demographic, housing, and planning research. The datasets encompass various themes pertinent to urban and regional studies, including some topic domains (e.g. education and employment) of interest to this project.

Australian Research Data Commons' Research Data Australia serves as a discovery tool for a broad range of data across disciplinary boundaries in Australia. Among others, its catalogue includes many data sets generated by research projects. NDHE (National Housing Data Exchange Platform) is a platform for sharing housing-related datasets among government agencies, researchers, and the housing sector. It is designed specifically to support evidence-based policymaking and analysis in housing, homelessness, and urban planning.

We examined how the different online tools address the identified information needs for early data discovery through their metadata field structures. When clicking on an individual data asset that is included in a catalogue or listing, a metadata field structure emerges. This structure is usually implemented under different section headings and, at times, through links to different pages or pop-ups on a website. Metadata fields were identified by their names/headings. We then examined how the metadata fields were used to address the primary information needs of early data discovery by scrutinising the content of these fields in some examples across the six data discovery tools. As the focus was on social science data, all data examples considered across the six tools were in a social science domain.

This process has at least two limitations:

² In Part 2 of this report which details technical specifications, we additionally reviewed the TERN Data Discovery Portal. It is not included in this section because it does not catalogue social science data.

1. In some data discovery tools, such as ADA Dataverse, the metadata field structure changes with the type of data. For example, sample surveys are documented using survey-specific fields, while historical Government records come with specific fields purposely built for such data. Also, within the same type of data, such as sample survey data, the number of fields can vary based on methodological peculiarities or some other matters related to the metadata generation process.

This limits the certainty with which our scan could identify all metadata fields under the different data discovery tools.

2. The type of content within a specific metadata field can change with different data sources, even if they are of the same type and within the same data discovery tool.

This limits an assessment of how content in a field addresses the identified information needs.

Due to these limitations Table 2, which indicates which metadata fields in the six selected data discovery tools address early discovery information needs to be read with some care. Despite these limitations, the undertaken scan is sufficient for the purpose of assessing how different metadata field structures used in commonly used data discovery tools address early discovery information needs.

1.2.1.2.2 *Summary of observations*

There were variations in metadata field structures across as well as within individual data discovery tools. These partially reflected specialisations for different types of data. For example, survey data listed in ADA (Dataverse), such as Australia's Disability Strategy Survey waves, contain metadata fields for Sampling procedure, Target sample size, Weighting and Response rate, matters specific to sample surveys and not applicable to (most) administrative data. Data catalogued in AURIN include metadata fields specific to spatial data, such as Coordinate reference system, Geometry field and Spatial.

Variations in metadata field structures also appear related to the disciplinary and occupational focus of a discovery tool. For example, the ADA tool is focused on social science data and specifically built to help social researchers in data discovery. This is reflected in metadata fields dedicated to population universe and collection method – information of high interest to social researchers.

In contrast, the Dataplace tool of the Australian Government has no disciplinary nor occupational focus. It offers a less detailed metadata field structure that does, for example, not entail the above-mentioned fields for sample surveys. Its metadata field structure (ONDC, 2023) instead emphasises administrative matters surrounding data – Data custodian, Point of contact, Access rights and Security classification constitute four of ten core metadata fields. Sensitive data, Legal authority, License, Disposal, Publisher and Related entities are additional fields, which are part of the Dataplace metadata field structure although they are less commonly populated with information. Data listings on other platforms also contain such fields. However, it is rare that all of them are included while lacking similar detail in the methodological domain, for example, when it comes to metadata fields that are dedicated to describing the scope of a population or the method of a data collection.

Differences in available metadata for administrative data may further reflect the disciplinary maturity of working with such data. The PHRN metadata structure contains explicit fields for Limitations and Data Quality Statement possibly reflecting a stronger tradition of using administrative data for research in health sciences. Such fields dedicated to outlining capabilities and limitations of data are virtually completely missing in all other data discovery tools. PHRN also offers a separate Purpose field, which was not present in data examples of the other five tools during the scan (although the ONDC (2023) metadata field structure that was used in Dataplace contains such a field). Further, the PHRN tool also features metadata fields for Variable list and Data dictionary, which cater for providing more microdata detail than the other tools.

AURIN's Attribute list seems equivalent to a Variable list, however, AURIN's catalogued data assets tend to have fewer variables than those catalogued by PHRN and ADA.

Most data discovery tools have a Description field. This is used in notably different ways across, but also within, data discovery tools, and can house various contextual, methodological and/or data publication information. For the examined tools that cover a wide range of disciplinary data (Research Data Australia and Dataplace), the Description field is the main or only field that can contain bits of methodological and contextual information necessary for effective early data discovery. In the examples examined (e.g. catalogued in Research Data Australia), some vital information (e.g. population scope) was commonly not included in the Description field. In the scan undertaken here it appears the more diverse disciplinary data is catalogued (Research Data Australia, Dataplace) the less metadata fields that are relevant for early administrative data discovery are provided. Effective early data discovery then largely hinges on the content in the Description field and/or the Related information field, both of which are generically defined in the respective metadata schemas behind Research Data Australia and Dataplace (ARDC 2025, ONDC 2023).

Having explicit metadata fields does also not ensure that these fields have relevant or any content. For example, in the data examples considered under the PHRN tool information in the Variable list and Data dictionary fields was not always available, highlighting the dependency of all data discovery tools on data owners/custodians for descriptions of their data, regardless of the structure of metadata schemas that are secondarily deployed.

Finally, metadata fields presented under Other information needs in Table 2 not only address later-stage data discovery needs, such as related to working with the data (e.g. Format, File size), but also prompt for information on administrative aspects around the production of the data (e.g. Funding, Producer, Production location, Publish date, Security classification) and/or the metadata (e.g. Version, Date modified).

1.2.1.2.3 Conclusions

Overall, each of the data discovery tools features a different metadata field structure at the data discovery end – where potential data users encounter information about data records unearthed by the discovery tools. Metadata field structures emphasise matters deemed especially important by the designers/administrators of the data discovery tool. Metadata fields, especially those defined as 'core' reflect what information should be systematically provided from the data discovery tool administrator's point of view. If a specific field, for example, a Population scope field, is not defined as part of a metadata schema used in processes of receiving metadata from data owners/custodians, the information it pertains to is more likely to not clearly be provided by those data owners/custodians in more generic fields, such as a Description field. This then generates ambiguities or gaps in the information provided to the administrator of the discovery tool that is transferred to the users of the discovery tool.

In relation to primary information needs in early data discovery processes outlined in Stage 1 in Table 1, the scan of discovery tools uncovered information gaps about:

- the purpose of the original collection/compilation (except PHRN where a Purpose field was provided and populated)
- the method of the data collection/compilation (except ADA in relation to survey data collections)
- the scope of the population (except PHRN that presented such information in a Scope field)
- general capabilities and limitations of the data (except PHRN when such information was provided under a Limitation and/or Data quality field)

In contrast other aspects of primary information needs about the data were covered by multiple data discovery tools, such as related to:

- the geographic scope of the data
- the temporal scope of the data
- the identification of the data
- the content of the data
- how and where data can be accessed or more information obtained

As was seen in some of the metadata record examples under PHRN, existing metadata fields in a secondary metadata schema (a schema, which is imposed on data owners/custodians post data collections by third parties) do not ensure that such information is regularly included in data records, which is plausible for at least two reasons:

1. the information was not generated by the data owner/custodian. This may particularly apply to Data quality statements when they are not available in the PHRN metadata field of that name.
2. providing the information faces some organisational barrier, such as related to resourcing or legal or political sensitivities. This may apply to Variable lists when they are not available in the PHRN metadata field of that name.

These observations and conclusions fed into the drafting of the metadata field structure.

Table 2. Primary information needs for early data discovery and metadata field structure in selected data discovery tools

Primary information needs for early data discovery	Existing metadata fields in selected data discovery tools for administrative data					
	ADA	Dataplace	PHRN	AURIN	Research Data Australia	NDHE
Identify data asset	Persistent identifier Title Subtitle Alternative title	Identifier Title	Name	Name ADP ID	Name/title Identifier	Name Id
Purpose of underlying collection	Description Series	Description Purpose*	Purpose	Description	Full/brief description	
Method and scope of collection/ compilation (how collected/compiled, unit of observation, sample/population/ coverage, geography, timeframes, how collected/ compiled)	Description Time period Date of collection Data type Geographic coverage Geographic unit Unit of analysis Universe Time method Sampling procedure Target sample size# Actions to minimise losses# Cleaning operation# Weighting#	Resource type Temporal coverage from* Temporal coverage to* Update frequency* Location*	Scope Collection temporal coverage Linkable temporal coverage Update frequency Linkage frequency Location Coding	Description	Full/brief description Spatial coverage Location Date time period	Temporal coverage Update frequency

	Collection mode Type of research instrument Series Characteristics of data collection situation [#]					
Data content (concepts, topics, variables)	Subject Keyword Topic classification Related publication	Description Keyword	Variables List [^] Data Dictionary [^] Other documentation FAQ	Type Attribute list	Subjects	Description Keywords (under Data and Resources heading)
Broad capabilities and limitations of data			Data quality statement [^] Limitations	Description		
What data may be accessible	Terms	Access rights Access URL [*]	Access rights	Access level Aggregation level	Access	Data and resources
Where to find further information about data and data access	Point of contact Request access Related information Related material	Point of contact	Contact information Approvals and governance	Additional info	Other information Contact information	
Other information needs	ADA	Dataplace	PHRN	AURIN	Research Data Australia	NDHE
	Publication date Author	Data custodian Security classification	Data linkage unit Data custodian	Last updated Created	License and rights	Author Maintainer

Related publication	Date modified	Legal authority	ADP ID	Authors	Version
Language	Publish date*	Language	Attribution	Related people	Last updated
Producer	Sensitive data*	Format	Coordinate reference system	Related data	Created
Production date	File size*	Metadata updated	Copyright notice	Related grants and projects	License
Production location	Format*	Publications	Data disclaimer	Cite	Attribution
Contributor	Language*		Geometry field	Notes	Spatial
Funding information	Legal authority*		Key	User contributed tags	Format
Distributor	License*		Spatial		Has views
Depositor	Data status*				Mimetype
Deposit date	Publisher*				Package id
Software	Related entities*				Position
Dataset version	Source*				State/status
					Groups
					Activity stream

Notes: The table is based on scanning of examples that were focused on social science (including health) data under each online discovery tool. This scan was undertaken between 17 and 23 December 2025.

These fields are not always included in data related to sample surveys.

*These fields are not included in the mandatory core attributes of the metadata structure so that these are often not provided by agencies submitting metadata to Dataplace and then not available in the tool.

^ Information in these fields is not always available, so that these fields can be empty.

1.2.1.3 Metadata field structure for SSRIN data catalogue

1.2.1.3.1 Introduction

The metadata template was designed by the SSRIN team to capture key information on data sources that satisfy early data discovery needs that could answer questions associated with general data discovery. This included questions such as ‘What kind of data exist?’, ‘What can the data potentially be used for?’ and ‘Are the data potentially useful for my research interest?’. The field structure was initially drafted by synthesising the primary information needs for early data discovery derived in Section 1.2.1.1 and the conclusions from examining metadata field structures related to six existing online data discovery tools that can discover administrative data (Section 1.2.1.2).

A draft template was then tested with a group of data analysts through a structured consultation process.

1.2.1.3.2 Draft metadata field template

Synthesising the learnings from the previous sections, metadata fields were drafted to balance utility to researchers, parsimony, and feasibility of collecting metadata. Table 3 outlines how the drafted metadata fields cover the earlier identified primary information needs for early data discovery. An additional information aspect was added at the end of Table 3 (Transparency of metadata generation), which relates to the credibility of the metadata information compiled during this process. Users of metadata need to have trust in the metadata they peruse. Sections in this report that document the process of how the data catalogue was compiled serve this purpose as does the Source of metadata extraction field in Table 3. All fields in the Metadata fields column in the table are considered to have a vital function in early data discovery.

While not possible for many fields, controlled vocabularies were used as often as possible to increase consistency and to simplify results. For example, DDI types of units of observation provide consistent descriptions of units. For categorising topics, a pre-defined set of categories is supplemented with more descriptive sub-topics which may be unique and are not controlled. The 11 pre-defined categories were derived from combining the Productivity Commission’s Report on Government Services (<https://www.pc.gov.au/ongoing/report-on-government-services/2025>) and the organisation of integrated data assets from the ABS (e.g., PLIDA) and DSS (e.g., the National Disability Data Asset (NDDA)). There were some additional fields considered but ultimately omitted because they did not respond to researchers’ most pressing needs. For example, field of research codes were considered, but did not adequately describe features of the data which would allow researchers to evaluate the utility of a given dataset for answering a proposed research question.

To improve usability across different types of data assets, small variations in the field structures were implemented in a template for documenting integrated data assets and another for documenting stand-alone, non-integrated, datasets (where indicated in the table).

Table 3. Metadata fields for SSRIN catalogue against primary information needs of early discovery

Information needs	Metadata fields	Content of field
Identification of data asset	Name	The (unique) name of the dataset or data collection from an official source (ideally the data custodian/owner).
Purpose of underlying collection and/or compilation	Purpose	A description of why the data was collected/compiled. Alternatively, when the purpose is not made explicit, this could include the original uses of the data by the government.

Information needs	Metadata fields	Content of field
Content of data	Main topics	The <u>main</u> topics (up to three) covered by the data translated into categories: 1-Demographics; 2-Organisationl characteristics; 3-Childcare, education, training; 4-Health; 5-Community services; 6-Social support/welfare; 7-Employment, income, taxation, wealth, consumption; 8-Housing, homelessness; 9-Justice; 10-Transport 11- multidimensional (for integrated data assets)
	Other topics	<u>Other</u> topics covered by the data collection using the same categories 1 to 10 from above. Can also be used when there are more than three main topics.
	Sub-topics	Topics within the broader categories.
	Inclusion into an integrated data asset*	States in which integrated data assets individual data assets have been integrated
	Component** datasets	Lists component data sets or modules which comprise integrated assets.
Method and scope of collection/ compilation (unit of observation, sample/population/ coverage, geography, timeframes, how collected/ compiled)	Population scope	The defined scope of the population in scope of the dataset outside the geographical and temporal scope.
	Geographic scope	The geographical and/or jurisdictional scope of the population covered by the data.
	Temporal range	The temporal range the data cover.
	Temporal unit/frequency	The temporal unit or frequency of the data collection.
	Unit of observation	A more detailed account of the unit of observation for which the data was originally collected/compiled.
	Type of unit of observation	Type of unit for which data has been originally compiled as per pre-defined categories adapted from DDI vocabulary for Analysis Unit. https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/vocabulary/AnalysisUnit
	Collection/ compilation methods	Brief information on the method/process of collecting/compiling the information, e.g. sampling, administration of collection, quality assurance, weighting. Includes data linkage where applicable.
Broad capabilities and limitations of data	Data quality (scope)	Information about the quality of data relevant to the scope or intended population coverage (e.g., statements of representativeness/bias).
	Data quality (other)	Information that additionally qualifies the data (e.g. statements of reliability of captured information). Could include statements by data custodians/owners or publishers for what the data could be used for.
What data may be accessible	Data access	Information about data releases, data access and associated links to websites/email details. This should include references to different units of analysis where applicable.
Where to get further information	More information about data	Link to authoritative resources with more metadata or contact details where more information can be obtained from an authoritative source.

Information needs	Metadata fields	Content of field
about data and data access	Data custodian/owner	The agency(ies) that own(s) the data (<u>has legal responsibility</u> for managing the data, including data disclosures and data protections) and/or manages data and data access
Transparency of metadata generation	Source of metadata extraction	URLs that point to the source(s) used for providing information on this data (collection) against the type of information sourced (if multiple sources were used for different aspects of the data) with the date information was accessed.

Notes:

*Only included in metadata field structure for individual data assets

** Only included in metadata field structure for integrated data assets

1.2.1.3.3 User consultations

The team then conducted external consultations with researchers to test the drafted metadata field structure for the SSRIN data catalogue (Low or negligible risk ethics approval was granted by the Human Ethics Committee of the University of Queensland (2025/HE000781)). Participants for user consultations were recruited from the SSRIN User Reference Group and existing networks and included researchers at various career stages in different institutional settings. Emails containing a link to the survey were distributed during June-July 2025, resulting in 12 completed consultations.

This approach purposely centred social scientists with interests and experience using Australian administrative social science data to produce novel research findings. This consultation process enabled the team to assess the practical relevance of the draft template and to refine its content based directly on the perspectives of potential end users.

Participants (n=12) were provided with the metadata template (similar to Table 3) and with a data example that was used to populate the template to increase the tangibility of the template. They were asked to reflect on the utility of the metadata field structure for early-stage data discovery. Specifically, they were asked: Are there fields included that are not important at the early stage of discovery? Is there anything missing from the template that would be vital for gaining a general understanding of administrative data? And is the level of detail sufficient to support an initial assessment of how the dataset might be used for social science research?

Most participants (n=8) agreed that all the fields included in the template were important at the early stage of discovery. There was also broad consensus that the level of information provided in the example was sufficient for forming a general understanding of the data.

Participants also identified some additional fields they considered potentially valuable. These included information on data format, opportunities for linkage with other data sources, variable lists, links to related datasets, and more detailed guidance on representativeness and ease of access.

These suggested aspects of information/fields had been either conceptualised to be relevant for later stages of data discovery in Table 1 (e.g. format, opportunities for linkage with other data sources, more detailed guidance on representativeness and ease of access) and/or appeared to be already covered by the drafted metadata fields. For example, the metadata field Data quality (scope) provides information on the representativeness of data, and the field Data access is dedicated to outlining data access options. As such the feedback did not so much question the metadata field structure but potentially the way these fields were populated in the example data record, which was influenced by the content rules for the fields and the ease with which information was publicly available.

In the light of the feedback, the team revisited the content rules for each field to ensure they were suitable for populating the fields and the detail with which information was provided in the example record.

The team also considered whether a field for Variable list should be added to the template. This was rejected for logistical and presentational reasons. The SSRIN catalogue focuses on discovering nationally-relevant administrative data assets, which are often based on large-scale and longitudinal data collections. The resulting data assets tend to have many variables, which can change over time. This makes providing accurate and complete variable lists challenging and from a presentational perspective, space-consuming. These may be reasons why variable lists were not often provided under a dedicated Variable list field in the example data assets considered under the PHRN data discovery tool. Ultimately, the provision of variable lists under different data discovery stages is one of scale. When data sets are small (e.g. cross-sectional with up to 15 variables), such as in some data (tables) that can be discovered with the AURIN online search functionality, a variable list can be seen as addressing primary information needs of early data discovery. When a data asset is larger in scale with dozens or hundreds of variables, a listing of subjects/topics addresses such needs. The SSRIN data catalogue was envisaged to only include larger scale data assets.

However, an important aspect of an early data discovery tool is providing an avenue for getting additional information, which is achieved by the 'More information' field.

1.2.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria for administrative data

Data assets could be included in the report if they met the following inclusion criteria:

- Australian administrative datasets, including integrated data assets, standalone administrative datasets, and components of integrated assets
- Datasets providing access to unit record-level data, with one of the following Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) units:³
 - Individual
 - Family or Family.HouseholdFamily (Family or Household family, referring to co-residing people related through family ties)
 - Household
 - OrganizationOrInstitution (Organization or Institution, e.g., schools, firms, hospitals)
 - EventOrProcessOrActivity (Event or Process or Activity, e.g., the completion of a specific degree/qualification, criminal conviction, etc.)
- Assets relevant to one or more of the following topical categories:
 - Demographics
 - Organisational characteristics
 - Childcare, education, and training
 - Health
 - Community services
 - Social support/welfare
 - Employment, income, taxation, wealth, and consumption
 - Housing and homelessness
 - Justice
 - Transport

³ <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/vocabulary/AnalysisUnit?lang=en>

- Enduring datasets, meaning they are regularly updated and form part of an ongoing data collection or administrative process

The following types of data assets have been excluded:

- Non-administrative datasets, including longitudinal surveys such as the Household, Income, and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) Survey and the Longitudinal Study of Indigenous Children (LSIC),⁴ cross-sectional social surveys, experimental or academic research datasets
- Non-enduring, ad hoc, discontinued, or one-off datasets, including historical administrative collections that are no longer updated or maintained and pilot studies or legacy datasets archived in repositories
- Aggregate or area-level datasets only, without access to individual-level microdata

1.2.3 Data search strategy

The search strategy for identifying administrative datasets relevant to social sciences in Australia involved a multifaceted approach that combined several tools and sources of information. The process included: (1) Treasury’s report “*Government Administrative Data Sources for Evaluation in Australia*”, (2025) on administrative data; (2) systematic searches of core data portals and platforms, such as Dataplace.gov.au and agency-specific websites (e.g., the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS), the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW)), where filters were applied to identify relevant datasets; (3) targeted searches of the following Commonwealth agency repositories: the Department of Education, Department of Health and Aged Care (DHAC), Department of Social Services (DSS), and Services Australia, to capture administrative data not centrally catalogued; (4) examination of integrated data assets such as the Person Level Integrated Data Asset (PLIDA) and the Life Course Dataset developed under the ABS’ Life Course Data Initiative and their components; (5) the research team’s prior knowledge of existing and discontinued administrative datasets (e.g. the Australian Migrant English Program (AMEP) and (6) broad Google searches to supplement other methods. This combined search process ensured broad coverage and increased the likelihood of identifying relevant, high-value datasets across multiple social domains.

Metadata were only included if they were accessible to researchers without prior approval. This means that metadata which are themselves restricted, such as variable lists for some data assets, were not included in the scan. For example, there is some non-public metadata about PLIDA which is held on secure DataLab servers which are only accessible to approved PLIDA users. This information was not included in the scan even though it is of use to potential researchers.

1.2.3.1 Treasury report

As a starting point for searchers, the research team drew on 2025 report from the Commonwealth Treasury, titled “*Government Administrative Data Sources for Evaluation in Australia*,” prepared by the Australian Centre for Evaluation. This report provides a comprehensive snapshot of the major administrative datasets available to support social science research and evaluation activities across Australia. Its key sections include:

- PLIDA which includes the PLIDA Modular Product and underlying data from agencies such as the ABS, DSS, and AIHW.
- Other linked assets: including the Australian Taxation Office (ATO) Longitudinal Files (ALife), the Business Longitudinal Analysis Data Environment (BLADE), longitudinal survey archives, AIHW assets, DSS collections, and state/territory linkage units.

⁴ Surveys or discontinued datasets were included if they formed a part of an integrated data assets, e.g. National Study of Mental Health and Wellbeing (NSMHW) and the Survey of Disability, Ageing and Carers (SDAC), which are included in the Person Level Integrated Data Asset (PLIDA).

- Major Commonwealth and agency-level sources, including the ATO, AIHW, Australian Institute for Family Studies (AIFS), and others, each summarised with their datasets, custodians, and access pathways.
- Finally, the report also lists state and territory data agencies and provides brief explanations about the jurisdictional linkage infrastructure (e.g., the Public Health Research Network (PHRN), the Centre for Health Record Linkage (CHeReL)).

1.2.3.2 Core portals and platforms

Additional searches were undertaken through the core portals and platforms to identify relevant administrative data. Searches on dataplace.gov.au were filtered by agency: ABS, AIHW, ATO, DSS, Department of Employment and Workplace Relations, Department of Health and Aged Care (DHAC), Services Australia, AIFS, Department of Home Affairs, Department of Education, and National Disability Insurance Agency (NDIA). Searches were also conducted on the agency-specific repositories, including ABS, AIHW, ADA Dataverse, data.gov.au, and CHeReL.

1.2.3.3 Targeted searches of Commonwealth agency repositories

Beyond central catalogues, targeted searches were conducted within the repositories of specific Commonwealth agencies, including the Department of Education, the DHAC, DSS, and Services Australia. This step was necessary because some administrative datasets are not indexed in centralised discovery platforms such as Dataplace.gov.au and can only be located through agency-level data portals or publications.

1.2.3.4 Integrated data assets

The search also extended to 17 major integrated data assets such as PLIDA and the Australian Census Longitudinal Dataset. Attention was given not only to the assets themselves but also to their modular products and underlying component datasets, to capture the breadth of data available through these linkage infrastructures.

1.2.3.5 Prior knowledge of the team

The research team's prior knowledge was applied to ensure that datasets known from past projects, including discontinued or poorly catalogued assets, were not overlooked. This approach allowed inclusion of significant but otherwise under-documented resources, such as the AMEP, which illustrate the evolving landscape of administrative data use in social science research.

1.2.3.6 Supplementary web searches

Finally, broad Google searches were undertaken to capture additional datasets referenced in grey literature, academic publications, and research reports. Results from these searches were subsequently cross-checked against other sources to verify their accuracy and relevance.

1.3 Documenting Australian administrative social science data

1.3.1 Documentation of process

Sources of truth

Data custodians/owners were considered as sources of truth in the process of compiling the data catalogue. These include agencies that collect the data under some legal authority, legally own the data, or manage the

data, including making determinations for providing access. Data custodians/owners may also develop data infrastructures, access and use protocols, or integrate data from multiple sources. While there are sometimes distinctions made between—and varying definitions of—data owners, data custodians, data publishers, and data stewards, all such agencies can be reliable sources of metadata for administrative data assets.

The metadata sources are documented for each data asset.

Relevant version(s) of metadata

Many administrative data collections are longitudinal in nature. Our inclusion criteria (see Section 1.2.2) further emphasised longitudinal data collections. Information about data collections or data assets commonly changes with new waves of collections or compilations. In compiling information about data assets, we prioritised information about a data collection or compilation that was most recently generated or updated. This was often, but not always, related to the most recently undertaken wave of a collection or compilation. At times information about data was not sufficiently available for all metadata fields of interest from the most recent metadata publications. Where possible, information for such fields was added from older versions of metadata.

URLs used for populating the metadata fields are documented for each data asset in the catalogue.

Carrying over information from sources

We identified relevant metadata – metadata, which fit the metadata fields in Table 3 – in existing documentation originating from relevant data custodians/owners. The information was carried over to individual fields by copying and pasting, paraphrasing and condensing text where necessary.

Paraphrasing was used for most scans to support consistency. In some cases, where the wording and tone of the original source closely aligned with the scans, information about the data asset was copied directly. Where possible, information was cross-checked across multiple sources to minimise the risk of factual errors.

Amount of information

The extent of information in our catalogue fields varies, which in part reflects variations of available metadata in the original sources. Some data assets are more complex than others and some data assets are more comprehensively documented than others. While our objective of facilitating basic data discovery did not require overly detailed metadata, we erred on the side of providing more information rather than less when such information was publicly available.

For each source, information was sought for every metadata field. Searching continued until relevant information had been identified from available data custodians/owners. For each field, the level of detail was guided by what would help a user (with a focus on early data discovery) understand at a high level what the data asset was about, what it covered, who held it and how it can be accessed. Where information was very lengthy, content was summarised.

Checking

Review of records

Ten standalone and six integrated data assets were randomly selected for review. Two team members went through five stand-alone and three integrated data assets each assessing:

- The appropriateness of the metadata source(s) used to extract information from – were they authoritative (primarily data owners and/or custodians)
- The accuracy of the content – was the metadata content in the current record of the data catalogue an accurate reflection of the content in the metadata source(s)?
- The extensiveness of the content given how much content was available in the original metadata sources and basic user data discovery needs
- The suitable allocation of content to metadata fields – was metadata content semantically suitably included under relevant field headlines? Did it follow content rules? Was this consistently done across records?
- Consistency in language – was the language used in the fields consistent across records?

The findings of the review of the 16 records are listed in Table 4. There was some duplication of information across fields within a single record and some inconsistency in the extent of metadata provided, which were both seen as not affecting the early data discovery function of the catalogue. Sources used for populating the 16 records were all primary sources considered as sources of truth. There was a very low prevalence of factual errors that appeared to be associated with typos and, on one occasion, with information related to another data asset.

Table 4. Findings of review of 16 records

Finding	Significance for data discovery
A 100% adherence to primary sources of information.	High
A very low prevalence of factual errors that appeared to be created by typos and misplaced pasting (once).	High
Some duplication of information across fields within the same record	Low
Some inconsistency in the amount of information provided (often reflecting publicly available metadata)	Low

Checking for accuracy assisted by Copilot

Factual accuracy is of high importance for effective early data discovery. We used the University of Queensland’s version of Copilot to identify potential factual errors throughout all 97 data records. We focused on metadata fields that describe the context and methodological aspects of the data providing Copilot with this initial prompt for checking the 80 individual datasets:

‘The attached html file contains information about 80 administrative data sets. The attached docx file contains a description of the metadata fields. Based on the descriptions in the docx file and using only information authored by data owners or data custodians, identify and document any factual errors in the following fields in the attached html file: Purpose, Population scope, Geographic scope, Temporal range, Temporal Unit/Frequency, Unit of Observation, Type of Unit of Observation, Collection and compilation methods, Data quality (Scope), Data quality (Other), Data custodian/owner.’

The html file with the 80 administrative data sets was attached to the query as was a table with the metadata descriptions which consisted of the Metadata fields and Content of field columns in Table 3. Successive interactions with Copilot were used to make the task more manageable for Copilot by defining batches of

data sets and reducing the number of metadata fields to look at in one request. Interactions were also used to define the structure of the output Copilot generated.

The initial prompt was then adjusted to apply to the 17 integrated datasets and run with the html file for the integrated datasets attached.

Copilot generated spreadsheets that showed the original content of a metadata field for a dataset/collection, whether it needs clarification, why and what content it suggested instead. A team member then went through these spreadsheets and checked all indicated cases by comparing the original against the suggested field content, perusing copilot's rationale for a change, looking at the broader documentation of the associated dataset in the data catalogue, and checking information against legitimate metadata sources.

The main observations from this process are summarised below:

- There is rich information in many fields for many data sets in the data catalogue, and Copilot often attempted to suggest more succinct and to-the-point-of-the-field descriptions. We retained the existing richer descriptions in the fields as they can be beneficial for understanding the data set/collection when reading the data record.
- There were very few clear factual errors picked up during this process. More commonly, there was some uncertainty about some features of the data, for example, in relation to different units of observations that may be part of the collections or associated data releases, or some ambiguity about a field's description. For example, in some cases the geographical scope not only relates to the population in scope of an underlying data collection but also to geographical levels of reporting. Again, we retained the additional information in such indicated fields as far as it did not compromise the understanding of the data.
- The most prevalent metadata fields for which content amendments could be legitimately suggested were: Unit of observation, Temporal range and Temporal unit/frequency. This possibly indicates that Co-pilot had, at the time of undertaking these checks, more obvious limits when it comes to checking wider content fields, such as for Collection/Compilation and Data quality.

A small list with suggested changes to content in metadata fields was created by the team member and then double checked by a second team member. Upon agreement among team members, a change was implemented in the data catalogue.

Checking durability of URLs

Compiling the data catalogue was undertaken over several months between April and September 2025. In December 2025 the URL links included in the catalogue were revisited. Seventeen of 458 links were 'broken' at that point in time. Links in the Source of metadata field were replaced with functioning links.

Disclaimer

The data catalogue relied on information sourced from data owners/custodians without checking for their accuracy or adequacy. This information was compiled between April and September 2025, with the exception of corrections made to broken links and accuracy checks detailed above. Thus, it represents a snapshot, and changes to data or metadata in the intervening months may not be accounted for.

1.3.2 Results of the environmental scan

After implementing the search strategy specified in Section 1.2.3, 80 stand-alone datasets and 17 integrated data assets were included for metadata extraction and inclusion in this report. All 97 included assets were

scanned by one researcher, with a 10% random sample reviewed by additional members of the research team. Full results are available in Attachment 1 for stand-alone datasets and Attachment 2 for integrated data assets.

More than half of the stand-alone datasets included in Attachment 1 (51/80) are components of one or more integrated data assets. Some of the stand-alone datasets are components of two or more integrated datasets, with Medicare Benefits Schedule (MBS) and Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) data collections being included in six integrated data assets each.

The included data assets come largely from Commonwealth government sources, with the ABS and AIHW among the most common data publishers. Other data publishers include DSS, the National Centre for Vocational Education Research (NCVER), the NDIA, Services Australia, DHAC, state and territory government agencies, and research institutes and universities.

Datasets were spread over the 10 topical categories, though there were clear concentrations in Health, Employment, income, taxation, wealth, and consumption, and Childcare, education, and training. Table 5 below shows how frequent each of the 10 topical categories was the 'Main Topic' of each of the 80 stand-alone datasets; Table X2 shows frequencies for the 17 integrated data assets.

Table 5. Main topics of stand-alone administrative datasets

Topic	Frequency	Percent
Demographics	5	6.2
Organisational characteristics	2	2.5
Childcare, education, and training	13	16.2
Health	26	32.5
Community services	5	6.2
Social support and welfare	2	2.5
Employment, income, taxation, wealth, and consumption	13	16.2
Housing and homelessness	7	8.8
Justice	6	7.5
Transport	1	1.2
Total	80	100.0

Among the 80 stand-alone datasets included in the review, 30% focused primarily on Health. Transport, on the other hand, was the main topics of one dataset, making it the least common topic across the reviewed data assets. The low number for Transport may reflect the search strategy which prioritised national-level data and was restricted to data about people or organisations, such as individuals' average commute times or access to public transport. However, administrative data assets related to this topic, such as maps of transit routes and ridership figures, may be relevant to researchers even though they fall outside of the scope of this exercise. Among 'Other topics,' Demographics was most common, suggesting that many datasets focused on social domains also include individual-level demographic characteristics which are often necessary for researchers to conduct meaningful analyses since they can contextualise findings and provide individual-level controls.

Table 6 shows main topic frequencies for the 17 catalogued integrated data assets. Unsurprisingly, integrated data assets were more likely than the stand-alone datasets to have multiple topics, thus earning the ‘Multidimensional’ label. Since integrated assets are by nature combinations of multiple datasets, even those assigned a single main topic often include more ‘Other topics’ than typical stand-alone datasets. The four assets where Demographic characteristics were the main topic all include the Census as a core dataset.

Table 6. Main topics of integrated data assets

Main Topic	Frequency	Percent
Multidimensional	5	29.4
Demographics	4	23.5
Organisational characteristics	1	5.9
Childcare, education, and training	1	5.9
Health	3	17.6
Community services	1	5.9
Employment, income, taxation, wealth, and consumption	2	11.8
Total	17	100.0

Geographically, most of the included data assets are national in scope. Temporal coverage and update frequency vary by data asset, with annual updates being the most common pattern. The predominant unit of observation is Individual, with other units such as Organisation, Household, and Event/Process/Activity represented in domain-specific data assets.

Three data access pathways are typical: publicly available aggregates; interactive table builders, and application-based access to microdata via custodians, often within a secure environment. While core descriptive fields (title, custodian, purpose) are usually present, key metadata, such as unit of observation (DDI), variable dictionaries, access and confidentiality conditions, and data quality statements are often absent or incomplete.

1.4 Discussion: Observations on discoverability of administrative data

Open datasets in Australia are generally straightforward to locate. National platforms such as data.gov.au, alongside state and territory open data portals, provide centralised access points for a broad range of government datasets. For the research community, Research Data Australia enhances visibility by aggregating datasets from universities, research institutes, and government agencies. By contrast, restricted administrative datasets—such as those that contain unit record data—remain considerably harder to discover. While catalogue entries often exist which merely confirm the existence of a dataset, the pathways to metadata, access conditions, and availability requirements are inconsistently documented or in some cases absent. Without this information, researchers are unable to evaluate the feasibility and utility of these data sources without investing significant time and resources into a potentially fruitless investigation of individual data sources.

1.4.1 Fragmentation of catalogues and portals

The fragmentation of catalogues and portals constitutes a central obstacle to discoverability of administrative social science data assets. Discovery takes place across multiple layers: Commonwealth, state and territory, sectoral domains (such as health, housing, and justice), and research-focused repositories. Agency inventories are often incomplete and not systematically updated. Our own searches also highlighted this issue: when revisiting several datasets only a few months later, some of the links to data resources had already become broken or inaccessible. This underscores the lack of maintenance and persistence in cataloguing practices, further undermining discoverability. Even within emerging initiatives such as Dataplace and the Australian Government Data Catalogue, the process of incorporating datasets remains ongoing. As a result, researchers often need to search across multiple portals before confirming whether a dataset exists and under what conditions it might be accessed.

1.4.2 Depth, consistency and accessibility of metadata

Metadata depth and consistency are also major limitations. Many records provide some basic descriptions, omitting critical information such as variable dictionaries, units of observation, frequency of updates, and data quality statements.

Among administrative data domains in Australia, health data assets are the most comprehensively documented. This reflects the role of the AIHW in defining national minimum datasets (NMDS), managing the METEOR metadata registry, and enforcing consistent data standards across Australia. Health collections usually provide variable definitions and quality statements, which improves discoverability and access. By contrast, domains such as housing, justice, or workforce often provide only high-level descriptions and lack the detailed metadata needed for robust research use.

The METEOR system operated by AIHW sets a benchmark in health and welfare, defining standardised data elements, value domains, and collection specifications. In practice—especially outside of health data—basic fields such as title, data custodian/owner and purpose are usually populated, but detailed variable definitions, linkage methods, and data quality information are rarely available. Some metadata is also inaccessible, e.g. in the case of PLIDA, where most metadata is only available inside the ABS DataLab secure environment, restricting discoverability during project scoping and proposal development phases.

Discoverability is further constrained by the limited use of persistent digital identifiers. The FAIR principles emphasise the importance of unique and persistent identifiers to support metadata interoperability, automated discovery, and accurate attribution (Wilkinson et al. 2016). AIHW's use of stable METEOR IDs offers one solution, but most administrative datasets lack DOIs or comparable identifiers, further limiting traceability and reuse.

The absence of a national individual identifier (comparable to Civil Person Registration number in Denmark) complicates linkage across datasets. Agencies rely on probabilistic or project-specific identifiers, creating technical challenges for integration and making metadata descriptions of linked datasets less transparent.

1.4.3 Naming of datasets and derivatives

Even once identified, documentation remains inconsistent. Frameworks such as the ABS Data Quality Framework and AIHW's data quality statement rules exist, but their application is uneven. Integrated data assets are particularly affected, with little published information on variable dictionaries or quality statements, making them difficult to assess and reuse. Confusion also arises between underlying data warehouses and derivative datasets. Multiple outputs may originate from a single warehouse, but are processed, curated, or labelled differently depending on the project, creating misleading discovery pathways. For example, AIHW's *Australia's Children* report lists the National Hospital Morbidity Database (NHMD) as a standalone dataset,

yet the associated link⁵ redirects to the broader National Hospitals data collection, which covers several sources without a dedicated NHMD description. The linked METEOR record instead points to the Admitted Patient Care NMDS, indicating that the NHMD is effectively a processed output of that NMDS. In practice, the terms “NHMD” and “APC NMDS” are used interchangeably, creating uncertainty for researchers seeking to establish the correct data source. A similar issue applies to the National Non-admitted Patient (episode-level) Database, which is not a standalone dataset but is derived from data supplied under the Non-admitted Patient National Best Endeavours Data Set and relies on its METEOR specification. Metadata rarely makes this relationship explicit, which may be misleading for researchers.

More broadly, distinguishing between a dataset, its derivatives, and its outputs is often unclear. For example, collections such as the NMDS and NHMD may be described interchangeably, even though one represents an underlying national minimum dataset and the other a processed derivative. This ambiguity risks duplication in catalogues or omission during discovery, as researchers cannot easily determine whether they are encountering the same data in different forms or genuinely distinct assets.

Other assets show the same issue. Within the NDDA, social security payments are described broadly as “Centrelink administrative data,” without specifying whether the source originates from the Data Over Multiple Individual Occurrences (DOMINO) module. However, the Office of the National Data Commissioner explicitly identifies DOMINO as a core component of the NDDA.⁶ This inconsistency illustrates how variation in naming and metadata can obscure the relationship between warehouses and derived datasets, complicating data discoverability for researchers.

Renaming of data assets makes discoverability even more challenging. In some cases, the process is straightforward and well-documented, as with the renaming of the Multi-Agency Data Integration Project (MADIP) to PLIDA. In other cases, renaming has been less consistent and more confusing. For example, the Juvenile Justice NMDS (JJ NMDS) and Youth Justice NMDS (YJ NMDS) both describe the same national collection of unit record data on young people aged 10 years and over under youth justice supervision in Australia. Initially reported as the JJ NMDS, the dataset was later retitled as the YJ NMDS to reflect updated terminology, and this name has been formally adopted by AIHW and jurisdictions. However, the earlier name remains searchable, without clear cross-references indicating that JJ and YJ refer to the same collection.

1.4.4 Custodianship changes, additions, and instability

Custodianship and agency naming changes introduce additional uncertainty for users. For example, while the AIHW was the original custodian of the National Health Workforce Dataset, custodianship was transferred to the DHAC in 2016. The Department itself has since been renamed several times (most recently the Department of Health, Disability and Ageing). Metadata records often refer simply to “the Department”⁷ without clarification, leaving ambiguity around the correct custodian and contact point.

Aside from changes in data custodianship, the landscape of Australian administrative data is fluid, with new assets emerging and existing ones evolving over time. The Better Evidence, Better Outcomes, Linked Data (BEBOLD) data asset in South Australia is a prominent example, expanding incrementally as new cohorts and data sources are incorporated. Comparable initiatives such as the WA Data Linkage System and Victoria’s GenV cohort also demonstrate this growth in state-based linkage capacity across health, education, and social services domains. However, the dynamic nature of these assets complicates

⁵ <https://www.aihw.gov.au/reports/children-youth/australias-children/contents/data-sources/administrative-data-sets>. Accessed on 25 July 2025.

⁶ <https://www.datacommissioner.gov.au/dsr-02467>

⁷ Australian Government Department of Health, Disability and Ageing (n.d.). National Health Workforce Dataset. Health Workforce Data. Accessed: 15 September 2025. [National Health Workforce Dataset](#)

discovery: scope and content change over time, documentation is uneven, and metadata is not always publicly available or standardised.

1.4.5 Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, while multiple sources were searched, the search strategy may not be comprehensive. Some relevant administrative social sciences data assets such as the ones kept in less visible agencies' repositories, may have been overlooked. Second, inclusion of datasets based on prior knowledge of the research team introduces subjectivity and potential bias. Third, many reviewed datasets lacked detailed or standardised metadata. This resulted in uneven descriptions across entries and limited the ability to make systematic comparisons. Fourth, the administrative data landscape in Australia is very dynamic meaning that the scan reflects only a point-in-time snapshot. Some of the datasets included may since have been updated, renamed, or replaced, while others may have emerged. These limitations mean that while the environmental scan provides a broad overview of the administrative social sciences data assets in Australia, it should not be considered as a complete catalogue.

1.4.6 Conclusion

This environmental scan report shows that the Australia's administrative data assets relevant for social science are extensive but not consistently findable. This means that collectively, administrative data assets in Australia are not as 'FAIR' as they could be, reducing their overall utility for research and informing evidence-based policy. Following the implementation of our inclusion criteria and search strategy, relevant administrative datasets for which metadata were available were concentrated within the domains of (1.) Health, (2.) Employment, income, taxation, wealth, and consumption, and (3.) Childcare, education, and training. Even within these domains, metadata availability is inconsistent, hindering discoverability for researchers and complicating early assessments of the feasibility of using a given data asset for research purposes.

Our findings highlight the need for standardised and comprehensive metadata for administrative data assets across topical domains and areas of government service delivery and administration. While administrative data are not designed for research purposes, providing accurate, up-to-date, and thorough metadata would enhance these secondary uses, make data more findable and accessible, and help to avoid mistakes in interpretation of research results. The lack of systematic and consistent metadata points to the need for a technical feasibility assessment of developing a perpetually updating, interactive data discoverability tool that consolidates administrative records and standardises essential metadata field

Part 2

Technical Solutions Report

2. Technical Solutions Report

2.1 Background

As noted earlier in Part 1 of this report, with the proliferation of administrative data assets, Australian researchers face challenges in finding and understanding the utility of administrative datasets. In contrast to data generated for research purposes, such as surveys, data custodians/owners often impose strict access controls for researchers or others seeking access to unit-record data to minimise legal and ethical risks. As a result, researchers often need to complete specialised data security training and submit detailed project proposals to gain approval to access data, and accessing these data often takes place in a secure data environment, either physically or via secure remote computing environments. This can be costly, in terms of both time and money, and as such heavily constraints early data discoverability as little information, including metadata, is available in the public domain.

Indeed, the administrative purpose of these collections also means that some metadata useful for social scientific purposes are often not created or made publicly available. Even if available, metadata are typically targeted at the originally intended users or creators of the data collection rather than social scientists who may access data for research purposes. While this orientation toward the primary uses of administrative data in documentation is understandable, it nevertheless creates barriers for social scientists attempting to obtain information about those data assets and assess their suitability for research purposes.

For social scientists who are unfamiliar with administrative data assets, discovering new data sources and making initial judgements about suitability can be effort intensive. They may not know where to look for data or metadata, or even whether the information they need to make those initial judgements exists. Unlike research-specific data assets like large longitudinal surveys where questionnaires, variable lists, and other metadata are well-publicized, administrative datasets often lack basic metadata or do not provide it in consistent formats or predictable, findable locations, which hinders data discoverability at early stages of the research process (such as assessing the general suitability of a particular data assets for a given research project). As such, consistently providing researchers with even basic metadata, such as a description of the main content of a dataset and key parameters such as the population scope, time period covered, and methods of collection, can help researchers quickly assess the dataset's relevance for their research purposes.

Ensuring that administrative data assets are findable and therefore consistent with the FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) requires that they be described with adequate metadata, allowing users to assess potential research uses of a data asset efficiently. A centralised catalogue as described in Part 1 of this report, and attached in Attachments 1 and 2, can aid discoverability and exposure of data assets, allowing greater exposure and use of administrative data assets, thereby increasing the public benefit of those data collections. A data catalogue is a tool that facilitates early data discovery allowing answering questions, such as: 'What kind of data exist?', 'What can the data potentially be used for?' and 'Are the data potentially useful for my research interest?'

To address these questions in relation to administrative data in Australia, the Social Science Research Infrastructure Network (SSRIN) conducted an environmental scan which catalogued 17 integrated administrative data assets and 80 stand-alone administrative datasets that are already available for use in social science research. This catalogue of 97 data assets represents the landscape of unit-record level administrative data in Australia as of 2025 within inclusion criteria specified in Part 1: Environmental Scan Report. It is currently presented as a static HTML catalogue (see Attachments 1 and 2), providing valuable—although compiled at a single point in time—information for researchers who are currently unfamiliar with

administrative data assets. The catalogue's format does not allow for sophisticated filtering or advanced searching beyond finding exact character strings. Part 2 of this report, focusing on technical solutions, outlines the challenges and opportunities in transforming the catalogue into an interactive, updateable tool for social science data discovery specific to Australian administrative data assets.

This part of the report proceeds with a section on an assessment of user needs and potential functionalities of such a tool, including a scan of existing data discoverability tools and consultations with research end users and data science and technology professionals with expertise on the technical challenges of creating a web-based interactive database. In subsequent sections we detail proposed front-end features and back-end functionalities of a potential resource, discuss technical and resource requirements of building and maintain such a resource, and conclude with a summary and future outlook.

2.2 Data discoverability tool: Assessing needs and functionalities

The project team undertook a number of activities to inform the potential design and features of a data discovery tool that would build and extend on the data catalogue compiled as part of the Environmental Scan. First, we undertook a scan of prominent existing online data discovery tools. As reported in the Environmental Scan Report (Part 1), we had investigated such tools to understand the metadata structures they employed and the metadata information they reported. Here our scan of such tools aimed at gaining insights about:

- how metadata information for these tools is compiled, and
- the functionalities these tools offer from the end-user perspective

Second, we conducted consultations with researchers to identify their needs and wishes for functionalities of such tools. This allowed us to identify gaps between users' needs and current functionalities of online discovery tools. Third, we consulted with professionals who build and maintain such online data discovery tools to understand the logistical implications and costs of building and maintaining such tools. In the final step we processed insights from all three steps to outline possibilities for adding functionalities to the SSRIN administrative data catalogue.

2.2.1 Scan of existing data discoverability tools

Selection of data discovery tools

We undertook a scan of existing online data discovery tools with an emphasis on discovering administrative data that have prominence in the Australian context to identify which functionalities these tools offer to users and how the underlying metadata is compiled. The data discovery tools were identified through targeted online searches and the research team's existing knowledge of national research infrastructure. They included online data search functions offered by:

- The Australian Data Archive (ADA Dataverse Catalogue, <https://dataverse.ada.edu.au/>)
- The Australian Government (Dataplace Australian Government Data Catalogue, <https://www.dataplace.gov.au/search/>)
- The Population Health Research Network (PHRN Metadata Platform, <https://www.phrn.org.au/resources/data-discovery/>)
- The Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network (AURIN Data Catalogue, <https://data.aurin.org.au/>)
- The Australian Research Data Commons (Research Data Australia, <https://researchdata.edu.au/>)
- The National Housing Data Exchange Platform (NHDE Portal, <https://housing-data-exchange.ahdap.org/>)

- Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN Data Discovery Portal, <https://portal.tern.org.au/browse/theme>)

ADA Dataverse specialises in national surveys in social science domains, such as the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics (HILDA) survey and the ANU Poll. Dataplace holds information for many data assets across disciplinary fields with most of the data assets falling outside the scope of social science data. Compared to ADA it offers discovery of more Government administrative data.

PHRN (Public Health Research Network) supports health and human services research by facilitating secure access to linked administrative and health datasets across Australian jurisdictions. It administers a metadata registry for data assets held by data linkage units and custodians, helping researchers identify available datasets and understand their structure, content, and linkage potential.

AURIN (Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network) focuses on spatially-structured urban and socio-economic data with an interactive GIS-based interface tailored for demographic, housing, and planning research. The datasets encompass various themes pertinent to urban and regional studies, including some topic domains (e.g. education and employment) of interest to this project.

Australian Research Data Commons' Research Data Australia serves as a discovery tool for a broad range of data across disciplinary boundaries in Australia. Among others, its catalogue includes many data sets generated by individual research projects.

NDHE (National Housing Data Exchange Platform) is a platform for sharing housing-related datasets among government agencies, researchers, and the housing sector. It is designed specifically to support evidence-based policymaking and analysis in housing, homelessness, and urban planning.

TERN's Data Discovery Portal focuses on environmental and climate-related data.

Of the seven data discovery platforms, the Australian Government Data Catalogue in Dataplace, the NHDP portal and the PHRN Metadata Platform have been more recent additions to the data discovery landscape in Australia all having been publicly launched since 2023 although PHRN data linkage projects date further back. Data discovery tools deployed by ADA, RDA, AURIN and TERN, under varying organisational arrangements, have a longer history and have experienced various upgrades over the years.

How metadata is compiled

Each of the data discovery tools reviewed features a different metadata field structure at the data discovery end – where potential data users encounter information about data in the records unearthed by the discovery tools. Simplified, the compilation of the metadata for all these tools occurs in three steps (Figure 1). Administrators of data discovery tools develop metadata schemas for their catalogues. These metadata schemas commonly follow metadata standards, some of which are listed below:

- DDI and DataCite (e.g. ADA),
- ISO 19115 and DCAT (e.g. AURIN, TERN, NHDEP),
- RIF-CS (RDA),
- Ecological Metadata Language (TERN)

All of the metadata schemas developed for the purpose of data catalogues aim at implementing the FAIR principles. In conjunction with metadata schemas, administrators of data discovery tools also develop metadata submission protocols, and associated processes and infrastructures.

Data owners/custodians then populate metadata according to the predefined structures and submit that data within the data discovery tool infrastructures. Alternatively, the metadata is harvested by administrators of data discovery tools into their systems after data owners/custodians have arranged the metadata according to the specifications by administrator. Data Services Teams within data tool administering organisations, to varying extent, then validate and/or enrich the ingested metadata.

Figure 1. Compilation of metadata for example data discovery tools, simplified outline.

Metadata provision, harvesting and enrichment can involve tools that automate parts of the process, such as related to transferring metadata to another metadata standard (e.g. using crosswalks), adding or transferring information to controlled vocabularies, keyword tagging or recognition of provided file formats (in the case data are provided with the metadata).

While metadata schemas are generated by data discovery tool administering organisations, data owners/custodians do not need to provide information in all relevant fields for their metadata (and often data) to be included in some of the data catalogues. Rather, only some of the metadata fields are designated as ‘core’/‘required’/‘mandatory’ and need to be addressed to comply with metadata submission requirements of data discovery tool administering organisations (e.g. see ADA 2025, ARDC 2025, ONDC 2023).

Regardless of metadata standards, metadata schemas and metadata management systems defined and implemented by data discovery tool administering organisations, the quality of the metadata accessible by users of data discovery tools then remains largely in the hands of the data owners/custodians. This also concerns updates to metadata. Data tool administering organisations can set up (automatic) metadata harvesting processes that include schedules of frequent harvesting; however, this does not affect the

currentness of available metadata to the end user when metadata are not updated by the data owner/custodian.

User functionalities

Table 7 outlines the user functionalities of the seven tools considered.⁸ All tools offer general open-entry search fields and browse functions, as well as search filters⁹ with predefined categories that reflect some of the metadata fields specific to the discovery tool. Another common function allows users to sort results, often by relevance, title/name and the date a record was created or modified.

Links to further metadata (also outside the offered metadata structure) are also relatively common. Apart from PHRN and RDA all other data discovery tool administering institutions considered here also have a data repository function. They offer links to preview and/or directly download data.

The platforms with a more academic research-focus – ADA, RDA and PHRN - include links to publications associated with using data from the data asset. The ADA facilitates downloading of citations for selected data assets.

In addition to general search fields and listed filters, some tools offer additional search functions, which allow combining multiple open-entry search fields in conjunction with the application of logical conditions for individual fields, and/or combining open-ended search fields and filters.

Some tools also come with one or more of the following:

- information bubbles/pop-ups for describing metadata search and filter fields
- a function to save search parameter
- a function to search results and/or expert search results
- a function to mark data records as favourites.

Table 7. User functionalities of discovery tools

Discovery platform	Open search field	Filters	Sorting of results by	Other
ADA	Yes	Yes	Name Date	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced search functionality offering the multiple application of up to 43 individual search fields/filters for data assets, six of which are categorical fields, plus 5 search fields for Dataverse • Information bubbles as popups containing brief descriptions of metadata/filter fields • Link for downloading data citation • Online contact form

⁸ To outline user functionalities in existing online discovery tools, different functionalities were solely considered from the user's point of view without testing the effectiveness of such functionalities or scrutinising their underlying technical implementations.

⁹ To outline user search functionalities in this section, 'Filter' relates to a field with pre-defined categories that can be selected in search processes. Categories of filters are commonly activated by tick boxes. However, filters here also include fields for defining the temporal and geographical scope of data assets, the former can be set up in different ways that allow open-ended entries that adhere to defined date formats, the latter can be set up to allow drawing rectangles or selecting areas on a map that de-facto select underlying geographical categories. 'Search field' relates to a field that allows open text entry and can be used in search processes. 'Field' can encompass filters and search fields.

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share function • Link to further metadata incl communications with potential respondents, questionnaires, data dictionaries, weighting procedures • Link for downloading data files • Links to publications produced from using the data
Dataplace	Yes	Yes	Relevance Title Newly added Data custodian	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced search function offering up to 14 individual fields/filters with some fields allowing open entry (e.g. for Description, Title and Keyword) and some categorical entry (e.g. for Data custodian and Security classification). Logical conditions for individual fields can be set (e.g. 'includes vs excludes' for searching in Description field, 'equal to vs not equal to' in Data custodian field or 'On or after vs Before' in Temporal coverage from field) • Links that extend from question mark symbols to provide a description of metadata fields • Exporting of search results • Links to preview and download data
AURIN	Yes	Yes	Relevance, Name Last modified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map selection and view of geographical scope • Links to additional information in metadata fields (e.g. under Description) • Links for downloading data
PHRN	Yes	Yes	No sorting function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information bubbles as popups containing brief descriptions of metadata fields • Links to detailed metadata if available (variable list, quality statement) • Links to publications produced with the data
RDA	Yes	Yes	Relevance Title Date added	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced search – query construction selecting 'contains vs excludes' options using up to six open-entry search fields individually or collectively (Title, Description, Identifier, Related people, Related organisations) • Save search • Save and export data records • Links to publications produced from using the data • Link for accessing data goes to data owner/custodian website, which can be associated with presenting metadata in a different metadata field structure, as well as presenting different content in the same field, such as different keywords.
NHDEP	Yes	Yes	Relevance Name Last modified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map selection and view of geographical scope • Links for going to data owner/custodian websites with additional metadata • Links for downloading data
TERN	Yes	Yes	Relevance Published Title Modified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map selection and view of geographical scope • Save search • Export results • Add to favourite records

- Links to external sources (of truth) with more metadata
- Links to associated publications
- Links for downloading data
- Exporting to DCAT, BibTeX, EndNote and Zotero

Notes: Terminology of ‘Advanced search’ functionalities have been copied from the respective data tools. No independent assessment has been made about advantages/ disadvantages of the seven tools’ user search functions.

While search filters are a universal user function of the seven data discovery tools considered, each tool offers a different filter structure in line with their underlying metadata schemas. Table 8 shows the filter fields for the seven tools. Many of the filters use vocabularies that are controlled by certain institutions for different disciplinary areas. These can deviate for the same filter field across data discovery platforms. The categories for the Subject filter in ADA Dataverse, for example, are very different from the categories under the same named filter field in RDA.

Table 8. Filters in discovery tools

Discovery platform	Fields that can be filtered
ADA	Dataverse category, Publication year, License, Author name, Subject, Keyword term, Distribution date, Series name, Data type, Time method, Unit of analysis, Geographic coverage country, Geographic coverage state/province, File type, File tag, Access (filter fields vary based on searching for Dataverses, Datasets or Files)
Dataplace	Access rights, Data custodian, Temporal coverage, Source, Demographic
AURIN	Location (select area), Organisation, Groups (access types), Tags, Licenses
PHRN	Jurisdiction, Collection type, Linkage type, Linkable temporal range, Resources available (Variable list, Data dictionary, Data quality statement) + filter for MBS, PBS, Hospital Admitted Deaths
RDA	Type, Subject, Data provider, Access, Access method, License, Time period, Location (drawing rectangles on a map)
NHDEP	Location (draw rectangle on a map), Organisations, Tags (analogous to keywords), Formats, Licenses
TERN	Region, Temporal range, Platform (ecological monitoring sites, mobile and fixed land platforms), Instrument (used for collecting data [e.g. laboratory, earth remote sensing instruments]), Parameter (variables measured in ecological datasets), GCMD (standardised keywords for classifying Earth science data), Fields of research, Australian Plant Name Index, Australian Fauna Directory, Horizontal resolution, Temporal resolution, License, Data provider, Author, Themes (broad categories that group datasets)

Notes: ‘Filter’ relates to a field with pre-defined categories that can be selected in search processes. Categories are commonly activated by tick boxes. Filters also include fields for defining the temporal and geographical scope of data assets, the former can be set up in different ways that allow open-ended entries that adhere to defined date formats, the latter can be set up to allow drawing rectangles or selecting areas on a map. Filters can be activated individually or collectively for a search.

The utility of search functions is generally influenced by the underlying metadata, the selections and open entries into search fields by users, and the functionalities of search engines that are deployed to execute searches. Only the first is briefly considered here.

There is a large dependency of the effectiveness of search functionalities on the metadata catalogued, and as noted in the Environmental Scan Report (Part 1), this largely depends on data owners/custodians

providing information according to metadata schemas developed by discovery tool administrating organisations. A simple example of the search implications of missing information in a metadata field is given here.

When Data was selected in the Type filter in the RDA platform on 12 January 2026, the selection resulted in 218,371 records (see Figure 2). Of those only 91,743 had a value assigned to one of the Field of Research (FoR) categories that could be selected under the Subject filter (Table 9). The FoR categories on this occasion were based on the Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC).

Figure 2. Screenshot from search on 12 January 2026

That 58%¹⁰ of the records have no value in the Subject filter is likely due to subject information not having been sufficiently provided to RDA, which in turn is likely related to Subject being defined as an optional field by ARDC in the metadata submission protocol (ARDC 2025). RDA allows building queries that include open-entry search fields, which can be used to discover data assets that may not be captured by the Subject filter. However, the point of the example was to demonstrate how filter functionality can exclude data from discovery at this point in the search process. Whether such data can still be discovered with the tool then depends on the user's search capability and on provided metadata in other metadata fields.

Table 9. Subject filter categories as per ANZSRC FOR and associated number of records when 'Data' filter was activated, RDA accessed on 12 January 2026

Subject	Number of records
Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences	7,773
Biological Sciences	24,180
Built Environment and Design	178
Chemical Sciences	486
Commerce, Management, Tourism and Services	78
Earth Sciences	7,064
Economics	99
Education	150
Engineering	2,087

¹⁰ The proportion could be larger if the same record has multiple subject codes assigned.

Environmental Sciences	4,670
History and Archaeology	39,378
Information and Computing Sciences	309
Language, Communication and Culture	628
Law and Legal Studies	1,011
Mathematical Sciences	118
Medical and Health Sciences	1,541
Philosophy and Religious Studies	69
Physical Sciences	582
Psychology and Cognitive Sciences	192
Studies in Creative Arts and Writing	380
Studies in Human Society	660
Technology	110
Total	91,743

In summary, there are large similarities across all seven discovery tools in search functionalities at the user end. Differences in filter search functionality pertain to fields that can be used as filters, which reflect differences in the metadata schema. Differences further relate to categories within the same-appearing fields due to the use of different controlled vocabularies for the same concept/field (e.g. Subject).

Some tools facilitate complex searches that allow the application of multiple open entry search and filter fields and logical operators simultaneously.

Metadata schemas substantially influence technically implemented search functionalities as search and filter fields are commonly aligned with metadata fields. Most online tools considered here did not make all fields from their underlying metadata schemas available as search filters or open-entry search fields.

This could plausibly be related to missing information in metadata fields because search results are also largely dependent on content having been provided by the data owner/custodian and/or derived in metadata enhancement processes by the data discovery tool administering organisation. Independent of the functionalities of specific search engines or query interfaces that can be utilised by users, operating search filters as a user can hide relevant data and prevent data discovery when information in the respective filter field was not provided by data owners/custodians. This highlights a risk that the availability of filters can unintentionally reduce data discovery when the relevant metadata is lacking and the mechanism is not obvious to some users.

Sorting, saving and export functions as well as information pop-ups and tagging favourites are other functionalities that are offered to users by some of the investigated data discovery tools.

Considerations in relation to the SSRIN Administrative Data Catalogue

Like in the seven examined cases, the development of the SSRIN metadata schema used for cataloguing administrative data assets was undertaken by the administrator (SSRIN). However, the SSRIN method of compiling metadata into the fields of the schema was different from all seven of the examined data discovery tools.

In the case of the examined data discovery tools, apart from some metadata enrichment activities, the metadata was provided by data owners/custodians according to schemas developed by data discovery administering organisations. This process, in large part, depends on the operational prioritisations, resourcing and motivations by the many metadata providing organisations who may not necessarily perceive a great stake in the data discovery tool for which they provide metadata.

For the SSRIN catalogue, the project team compiled the information from data custodians/owners into the SSRIN metadata schema. This made the compilation process dependent on only one institution, which was also an institution with a vital interest in building an early data discovery resource. While the SSRIN process may introduce a risk that available metadata information is misinterpreted in some way, the centralisation of interpretation of available metadata also increases the chances that all or many of the fields of the metadata schema introduced by the data discovery tool administrator are populated and that they are populated with a high degree of semantic consistency.

Completeness and semantic consistency of metadata have positive implications for considering adding field-specific search and filter functionalities for the SSRIN administrative data catalogue as they significantly reduce the risk of missing data records in search processes that emanates from deploying search and filter fields that are tied to entries in metadata fields.

Given the current number of data assets in the SSRIN administrative data catalogue is not very high, other user functions may currently be less vital although the deployment of saving and export functions, the application of information bubbles for describing metadata fields and favourite markers for individual data assets could be considered in defining options for adding functionalities to the catalogue.

2.2.2 User consultations

As part of our process for gathering user perspectives, we developed an online survey to capture the views of users of data discovery resources on the functionality of these tools in general, as well as on the potential development of a new tool. The survey details, recruitment strategies and participant demographics are described in Part 1 of this report. Participants were asked the following questions about the characteristics of a potential new data discoverability tool:

If an online or interactive version of a data discoverability database and tool were created, what would be desirable technical functionalities (e.g., filtering mechanisms, advanced search functionality, etc.)? How would these capabilities help you as a user?

Responses about desirable technical functionalities broadly fell into two categories: improved search and filtering functions, and AI assistance. Suggestions for search and filtering enhancements included the ability to amalgamate or align data across time points (for example, lining up participant responses over time), searching by data item description, and supporting phrase-based searching to accommodate differences in terminology across disciplines. Participants also highlighted the need for more granular and flexible ways to narrow results by topic, geography and temporal scope, including enhanced filtering and sorting mechanisms and more advanced search options. Some respondents proposed interactive comparison features, such as being able to “hold” a set of datasets for specific geographies or topics and compare them side-by-side in a more visual or interactive way.

Several participants suggested that AI assistance could further enhance the tool's usability and accessibility. In particular, integrating a large language model (LLM) was seen as a way to enable plain-language querying, allowing users to describe their research question and receive relevant dataset suggestions with links back to the catalogue. One participant proposed a Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) approach, combining a general-purpose LLM (for example, ChatGPT) with a defined knowledge base so that responses remain grounded in the catalogue content. They noted that this could support iterative exploration

through follow-up questions. Related comments emphasised that query-based functionality would be especially valuable for researchers who want to enter a research question (for example, about chronic health conditions and employment outcomes) and be guided to datasets relevant to that topic. Searching by data item description was also identified as important in fields such as higher education research, where terms such as “faculty” or “study area” may not be consistently represented across metadata; some participants suggested this may be well suited to an AI-assisted approach.

Additional suggestions focused on strengthening the underlying metadata foundations. Participants noted the importance of clearly defined metadata fields so that catalogue developers and users share a consistent understanding of what each field represents. They also emphasised the value of including information about potential linkage and practical access pathways, such as contact details, application links and indicators of whether datasets can be linked or combined.

2.2.3 Technical expert consultations

Following the review of existing data discoverability tools and consultations with researchers as end users of a potential data discoverability tool, we consulted with a range of technical experts with backgrounds in data science, social science, and information technology. The aim of these technical expert consultations was to build an understanding of the technical requirements and options for transforming content from the Environmental Scan Report into an interactive discoverability tool that would allow researchers to discover and assess the initial suitability of potential administrative social science data sources.

We conducted seven consultations with 12 total individuals (mean duration of 51 min. (range – 38-59 min.)). In many cases, the technical experts had experience operating data catalogues with similar user interfaces as the existing data discoverability tools with search and filtering features reviewed in Section 2.2.1. Other technical experts we consulted had expertise in research computing infrastructure. Consultation participants were recruited from the SSRIN Technical Reference Group and through professional networks.

A key difference between many of the consulted experts’ experiences and a potential SSRIN data discoverability tool is that the data catalogues or platforms that our technical experts had worked on generally catalogued actual data as well as its associated metadata. Most of the datasets catalogued in the technical experts’ experiences were openly available and downloadable for researchers. An example of such a data platform might include the TERN Data Discovery Portal, which automatically uploads environmental data collected from various sensors. Our focus on unit-record administrative data, on the other hand, would not allow for hosting or linking to actual downloadable data given data custodians’ requirements to restrict data access given their sensitive nature. This difference led the technical experts to suggest paths for SSRIN that were often different from their own experiences, providing more cost-effective and less technically demanding solutions.

2.2.3.1 Data management systems and interfaces

Data management systems are a category of software that allow for the storage, organisation, and publication of data or metadata and may be used to create metadata catalogues, among other outputs. Prominent examples of data management systems include CKAN and Dataverse, among others (Boch et al. 2022). A data management system would allow for implementing both back end (i.e., non-user facing) and front end (i.e., user-facing) products. The back end of a data catalogue would contain an interface for collecting, inputting, and organizing metadata; the front end would present appropriately formatted information to users based on data or metadata held in the back end.

Technical experts suggested that there were three broad paths available for building an interactive, web-based metadata catalogue. The most labour-intensive option would be to create a custom database management system from the ground up. This option had been used by several of the experts we consulted.

The benefits of creating their own software solutions were that it was customised to be fit for their purposes. This meant that everything from a data entry interface on the back end (i.e., not user-facing) to front-end user experience considerations could be built from scratch and optimised for the given data catalogue's purpose. The major downside of a customised, in-house software solution is that it requires much more developer expertise and labour. For data catalogues with more specialised technical needs, the benefits of customisation might outweigh the costs of employing a team of developers. However, given the relatively simple technical requirements of a metadata catalogue that would be unable to host or query administrative datasets due to technical and legal constraints, the technical experts we spoke with suggested that these benefits would be limited in our case. Thus, they universally recommended against building a fully custom platform.

Rather than building a custom platform, consultation participants recommended using one of several preexisting data management systems. These could be divided into two groups: commercial solutions and open-source solutions. While commercial solutions might offer some benefits, such as potentially having more modern features or providing in-house technical support, consultation participants were sceptical of the cost-to-benefit ratio of these paid services for our research-specific purposes.

Instead, they tended to suggest utilising an open-source data management system which has the advantage of being free to implement. Such data management systems are customizable, meaning that their 'off the shelf' capabilities can often be enhanced by providing bespoke metadata fields, customising advanced search or filtering features, and other enhancements which might be implemented by software developers building a potential tool. Further detail about open-source data management systems is provided in Section 2.3.2.1.

These suggestions about potential data management systems fit what the technical experts saw as a metadata catalogue's main functionality needs: a database of information organised using a consistent field structure which could be browsed, filtered, searched, and queried by users in flexible ways. In this way, suggestions from technical experts were practical and could feasibly be implemented with relatively manageable budgets. Other, perhaps more innovative user interface options, such as LLM integration, were also discussed during some of the consultations. Opinions were inconsistent about the use of LLMs in this context. While some of the experts we consulted were currently in the midst of developing AI- or LLM-based tools that allowed users to interact with chatbots to query data or ask questions about metadata, others were sceptical of the accuracy of LLM responses given metadata that might be inconsistently created or published. Another consideration with LLM-based interfaces was the technical expertise required to build them. The examples of in-progress LLM-based interfaces required relatively large teams of AI developers, which would increase budgets during the build phase. Open questions remain on whether these initial costs might be recouped over time if LLM-based interfaces proved more capable than a traditional metadata catalogue (e.g., by reducing maintenance or updating costs) or whether the initial costs might decrease in the future as LLMs become more commonly used or as innovation renders subsequent LLM "reasoning models" more common and less susceptible to inaccuracies.

Additionally, many of the most impressive benefits of LLM-based interfaces related to their ability to query and analyse data. For example, some consultations demonstrated prompting an LLM chatbot with an empirical question that could be answered using data held by the tool, which would not be possible with current restrictions around the unit record administrative data assets catalogued in the Environmental Scan Report. Still, similar abilities to interact or 'converse' with a chatbot-style LLM might be useful if more complete metadata were consistently available. For example, if complete variable item lists and values were available, users might be able to ask an LLM-powered chatbot questions about the feasibility of a given research question. However, given the generally inconsistent provision of variable lists and other detailed, machine-readable metadata by administrative data custodians/owners, such functionality would not be immediately implementable.

2.2.3.2 Web hosting

Another key consideration discussed with technical experts was web hosting. Similar to the options laid out for data management systems, there were free and paid options. While technical experts suggested that costs to commercial web hosting services would be limited given the relatively simple design of a metadata catalogue, they tended to suggest utilising the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud (Nectar), a free web-hosting service for Australian research use created by the ARDC. Further detail about web hosting services is provided below in Section 2.3.2.2.

2.2.3.3 Building and maintenance

The technical expert consultations were also useful in providing some estimated timelines for building a relatively simple metadata catalogue and providing insights into ongoing technical maintenance requirements. Estimates for building a CKAN or Dataverse instance based on the field structure used in the Environmental Scan Report were in the range of roughly six months for a full stack developer, with ongoing technical maintenance of much less than a single full-time equivalent developer. It should be noted that these estimates of maintenance costs related only to keeping a static database live and functional, but that any content updating or expansion would necessitate further resources. Several experts we consulted with suggested that automating as much maintenance as possible, such as with scripts to find and report broken links, helped to reduce costs. They suggested that many of these tasks could be built into the data management system and that extensions already existed for platforms like CKAN or Dataverse to implement such functionality.

The consultation participants also stressed the importance of content experts familiar with the included and potential datasets working closely with the software developers to provide oversight and ensure that the technical implementation matched researchers' needs as end users. Multiple experts also suggested that a content expert (i.e., a social scientist) should have oversight over all of the content because there was a subjective element to metadata collections. Strong leadership by a content expert was seen as necessary to achieve a level of consistency across data sources.

2.3 Features and functionality of a web-based interactive metadata catalogue

2.3.1 Features and user experience

When it comes to tool features, the key requirement is that the interface helps users quickly understand whether a data asset exists, whether it is likely to be relevant, who holds it and how it can be accessed. The purpose is to do it without forcing users to navigate multiple external catalogues. Based on the feedback from users and technical experts, the tool should be a web-based, searchable metadata catalogue, comparable in overall function to existing discoverability platforms in Australia but optimised for social science discovery tasks.

2.3.1.1 Search and filtering

The homepage should prioritise immediate entry into the discovery of data assets. Drawing on findings from our user consultations and relevant research evidence (Miller et al., 2025), the primary entry point should be a prominent search function that supports both broad keyword searches and targeted lookups. In parallel, the homepage should provide clear, intuitive browsing pathways that reflect how social scientists typically scan the data landscape, including browsing by substantive domain (for example health, education, justice, transport), collection type, and geographical coverage. To ensure equitable access to discovery and use in

university research environments, the application must meet Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2 AA requirements,¹¹ including accessibility across search, filtering, navigation, and metadata presentation.

Search and filtering functionality should be explicitly designed around common early discovery tasks in social science research. These tasks typically include initial relevance screening, units of observation checks, confirmation of construct presence, assessment of temporal feasibility, evaluation of scope and access conditions, and consideration of linkage potential. While existing discovery tools often support basic identification through geography, temporal coverage, and dataset titles (see Section 2.2.1), they do not always provide consistent, structured information on the purpose of the collection, how the data were collected or compiled, the scope of the population, and high-level limitations or data quality. These elements are critical at the early discovery stage because they enable researchers to make quick decisions about whether a dataset could plausibly address a research question, before investing time into further investigation or formal access requests.

The interface should therefore prioritise structured metadata fields and a visible presentation of these elements to support early feasibility assessment. This design requirement directly addresses limitations observed in existing multi-disciplinary catalogues where methodological and contextual information is often confined to a generic Description field or omitted altogether (see Section 2.2.1 above).

Faceted filtering should allow users to narrow results by subject area (using controlled vocabularies where possible), geography, temporal coverage, and unit of analysis. Field names and their intended meanings must be defined centrally and applied consistently across the tool to ensure that filtering remains interpretable and reliable over time. Consultations with technical experts highlighted that discovery tools tend to degrade when multiple contributors populate fields using divergent interpretations. A practical mitigation is to assign responsibility for defining and maintaining search and filter fields to a designated team member or small governance group, supported by agreed definitions, controlled vocabularies, and validation rules applied at data entry.

Filters that support rapid judgements about currentness and maintenance are also essential, including filtering by last metadata update date and known update frequency. Where access-related metadata is publicly available, it should be presented in a clear and consistent way using a small, controlled set of access modes (for example public, by request, restricted, or unknown), with “unknown” explicitly used where public information is insufficient.

In addition to flexible faceted filtering, users should be able to restrict searches to a single source database or to a defined set of databases, and to save search and filter configurations for reuse across sessions and projects. Because early discovery usually involves running a search, scanning the results, and quickly refining the query multiple times, the interface should provide immediate and transparent system feedback for longer-running queries. For example, if search execution exceeds a short threshold (such as two seconds), users should see a clear indication that results are still loading, along with options to refine filters or cancel the query, rather than encountering an unresponsive screen. Search results should support quick initial assessment by displaying a short description and the most decision-relevant metadata fields at a glance. Once users have selected a data asset to investigate further, they would navigate to an asset-specific landing page designed to support quick feasibility assessment, unlike the html attachments which are presented in an offline, sequential format.

A related assets section should support discovery beyond single records by bringing together links to connected resources that help users interpret, compare, and operationalise the dataset, including related datasets (e.g., thematically linked collections), dataset series and key supporting documentation such as

¹¹ Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2 (<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG22/>)

data dictionaries, metadata schemas, quality statements, linkage descriptions, and methodological notes that help users to understand the content and suitability of the data for a given research question. Where possible, records should be assigned stable URLs so that discovery itself can be cited and reproduced within research workflows.

Navigation should support exploration across collections rather than limiting users to a one-record-at-a-time experience. This can be achieved through explicit, meaningful links between related assets using clearly defined relationship types, such as derived from, supersedes, common linkage partner, or same custodian. A structured set of relationship types implemented through controlled vocabularies and consistent metadata fields can support plausible discovery pathways.

Finally, users should be able to interact with discovery results in ways that support research practice. This includes the ability to save or shortlist records during a session without requiring an account, export result sets in simple, interoperable formats (e.g., CSV, .json), and generate shareable links to search queries so collaborators can reproduce the same discovery set. A comparison view that allows a small number of datasets to be compared side-by-side on core metadata fields is particularly valuable for social science discovery, as it supports structured assessment of suitability without requiring users to open multiple pages. Throughout the interface, missing or incomplete metadata should be visible and explicitly signposted. This improves transparency for users and provides a clear basis for prioritising metadata improvement over time.

In the longer term, there is potential to incorporate LLM-based functionality as an optional assistive layer, but its use should be treated with caution. In our user consultations, two participants explicitly advised against using LLMs due to concerns about lack of transparency and the risk of errors. Consequently, the best approach would be to limit LLM use to functions which do not introduce new claims, such as helping users translate natural-language questions into structured filters, suggesting relevant keywords and controlled vocabulary terms, or summarising what is already written on a dataset landing page using only the on-page metadata. The key design requirement is that any LLM output is fully grounded in retrieved metadata and always provides links to the records and fields it used, so users can verify rather than trust the model's wording.

2.3.2 Functionality and back-end design

This section outlines the technical options for delivering the functionality described in the previous sections, including back-end architecture, hosting arrangements, and mechanisms for ongoing maintenance. The emphasis here is on selecting sustainable solutions that support metadata-focused discovery, are feasible to operate within research infrastructure constraints, and are aligned with established Australian research data practices. As such, the preferred approach is to build on established, open-source data management systems. While a fully custom-built option can offer maximum flexibility, the project's limited technical complexity means those benefits are likely outweighed by the increased expense and specialised expertise required to develop and maintain a fully custom system. By contrast, off-the-shelf open-source platforms have well-documented software with established user and developer communities, which can reduce the amount of custom-written code and make it easier to recruit staff with relevant skills.

2.3.2.1 Data Management Systems

Following consultations with technical experts (see Section 2.2.3.1 above), CKAN and Dataverse emerged as leading candidates for open-source data management systems. Both provide integrated front-end and back-end functionality, developed APIs, and established user communities.

Initially released in 2007, there are now more than 50 documented CKAN 'data hubs' in existence globally. CKAN is an open-source data portal platform focused on publishing and discovering datasets. This is a 'copyleft' license which requires other developers to make any code that they develop for a public CKAN

instance available under the same license conditions. As such, it requires ‘reciprocity in perpetuity’ among developers who work with it, and provides a dataset catalogue, rich APIs, and optional storage/indexing via the DataStore. CKAN also offers numerous extensions through plugins (e.g., harvesters used to automatically import data, map viewers). Australia’s national open data portal and several state portals run on CKAN.

Dataverse is an open-source repository platform for sharing, citing, preserving and exploring research data, designed for universities and research organisations. It emphasises rich, standards-compliant metadata, persistent identifiers (DOIs/Handles), file-level controls (including restricted files and embargoes), and tools for tabular ingest and exploration. Dataverse is typically hosted by universities, research consortia, and repositories with more formal governance and version control (e.g., Harvard Dataverse, AUSSDA, Odum Institute).

Below, we provide an overview and comparison of these two data management systems (Boch et al., 2022; Mahato & Gajbe, 2018) along axes relevant for metadata collected in Attachments 1 and 2 (additionally, see 0 for a table comparing some technical features of Dataverse and CKAN).

2.3.2.1.1 Key features and differences: comparison between Dataverse and CKAN

Organisation of content and features

CKAN organises content based on groups, organisations, or datasets. A dataset can belong to a single organisation, and each organisation controls access to its datasets. Groups are aimed at the creation of collections of datasets.

Dataverse has a root dataverse which is the main container. Within this root dataverse, there can be other dataverses, and each of these dataverses can publish data under a different subset (dataset).

Both DMSs contain similar discovery features (see Table 10), with integrated search and advanced search features. CKAN and Dataverse also both offer citation exporting and persistent URLs and DOIs to identify datasets, though CKAN requires an extension.

Table 10. Content Discovery Features

Content discovery	Dataverse	CKAN
Integrated search engine	Yes	Yes
Advanced search with facets	Yes	Yes
Full text search indexing	Yes	Yes
Browse options	Yes	Yes
Graphical navigation of content	No	No
Relocation tools	Yes	Yes
Search engine optimisation	Yes	Yes
DOI and persistent URLs	Yes	Yes (through extension)
Citation export	Yes	Yes

Metadata and standards

CKAN's default metadata schema is very simple but can be extended and customised based on need.¹² In addition to its own default schema, CKAN supports DUBLIN CORE and DCAT via extensions.

Dataverse's metadata schema is designed around the DataCite citation standard and contains more fields than CKAN does by default.¹³ Dataverse also allows for the creation of "metadata blocks" tailored to each discipline, though this feature may be less important in a metadata catalogue aimed at general, early-stage discoverability in the social sciences. It is modular but the base "Citation Metadata Block" is always included. Like CKAN, Dataverse also supports additional metadata schemas, including DUBLIN CORE and DDI. Both CKAN and Dataverse metadata schemas are customisable, and consultations with technical advisors suggested that either platform would be able to incorporate the metadata fields considered in the Environmental Scan.

API support

Application programming interface (API) is a set of subroutine definitions, protocols and tools for building application software. Basically, it is a set of defined methods of communication between various software components. A good API makes it easier to develop a computer program by providing all the building blocks.

Dataverse allows users to develop their own API for interoperability in addition to established protocols (e.g., SWORD API) which allow non-Dataverse software to deposit files and metadata into a Dataverse installation and Search API, which allows API clients the same searching, sorting, and faceting operations as the Dataverse web interface.

CKAN's Action API exposes all the core functionalities of CKAN to API clients. Everything that can be done using the web interface of CKAN can also be done through the CKAN API. Thus, both CKAN and Dataverse allow users to interact with their API to perform searches or extract information in automated, machine-readable ways.

Storage options

Dataverse provides support for S3 (Simple Storage Service)/S3-compatible storage, which is used by several commercial cloud storage companies. It can connect directly to these storage systems without extra coding, reducing development costs. Data can be stored on the server or in a cloud. CKAN keeps data in two main ways: FileStore and Datastore. To use other options, CKAN requires plugins or extra configurations. However, because the metadata catalogue from the Environmental Scan currently contains only metadata, without attached files or resources, Dataverse's advantages in file storage may be less salient than they would for data depositories, such as the ADA Dataverse.

2.3.2.2 Hosting options

ARDC Nectar Research Cloud emerged as a primary hosting option during our consultations with technical experts, as discussed in Section 2.2.3.2. Nectar provides Australia's national cloud research computing service, enabling scalable compute, storage, and application hosting within a research-governed environment. From a strategic perspective, hosting on Nectar would be cost-effective and aligned with ARDC-supported infrastructure. On the other hand, some users raised practical concerns based on their

¹² CKAN's default metadata schema includes fields for: Title, ID, Description, Group, Organisation, Tags, License, Author, Author email, Maintainer, and Maintainer email for 'Datasets,' and fields for: Title, Description, Format, and File ID for 'Resources.'

¹³ Dataverse's default metadata schema includes fields for: Title, Author, Contact, Description, Subject, Keywords, Related publications, Producer, Production date, Distributor, Depositor, Deposit date, Language, Persistent identifier, Version number, License/Terms of use, and Access conditions for 'Datasets,' and fields for: File name, File type/format, File size, Description, Tags, Checksum (for integrity verification), Restriction status, and Persistent identifier for 'Resources.'

experience with Nectar-hosted prototypes, including variable performance, intermittent availability, and limits on disk and compute resources. These constraints may limit suitability for higher-load usage, though the relatively small size of the metadata catalogue—along with the fact that it would not be used for hosting large data files—suggest that risks related to higher-load usage may be small. Thus, while paid commercial web hosting services offer mature, widely-used options and might provide scalable performance, the benefits of the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud likely outweigh its risk in this application.

2.3.2.3 Back-end data entry and maintenance

The data entry back end should support consistent capture of discovery-critical metadata for administrative social science datasets. Forms should be organised around researcher feasibility assessment (purpose, population scope, unit of observation, temporal coverage, geography, and access pathway), with controlled vocabularies, required fields, and basic logic checks to prevent inconsistent entries. The back end should also capture provenance and currency, store documentation links in dedicated fields to support automated link checking, and support a simple draft->verify->visible workflow. The purpose of a draft->verify->visible workflow is to protect the reliability of early-stage discovery while allowing the catalogue to grow over time. Batch import and bulk editing functions are required to enable scaling beyond the initial dataset set, while role-based permissions and centrally maintained field definitions protect consistency as multiple contributors become involved.

2.3.2.4 Automation and quality assurance

For a new social science data discoverability tool, automation should be targeting the reliability of discovery-critical metadata over time. The purpose of automation is not to enrich content or infer new information, but to ensure that the metadata researchers rely on for early feasibility assessment remains present, interpretable, and current as the catalogue expands. Thus, scheduled scripts should verify that each dataset record continues to have a defined discovery profile, including fields that directly support early selection decisions: purpose of the collection, population scope, temporal coverage, unit of observation, access conditions, and last metadata update date. These checks help ensure that datasets remain comparable in search and filtering, and that missing information is made explicit rather than silently degrading discovery behaviour.

Automated validation should also enforce agreed controlled vocabularies and basic logical constraints where these underpin search functionality. For example, scripts can flag records where access status is not one of the approved options (public, by request, restricted, or unknown), where temporal start and end dates are inconsistent, or where unit-of-analysis fields are missing or populated using non-standard terminology. This is especially important for administrative social science data, because metadata is often contributed by different organisations over time.

Link checking is a further priority. Manual checks of links across the 97 datasets, conducted three months after the initial scan, showed that approximately 3.5% of the links (17 out of 458) were broken. While manual checking is feasible at this scale, it is unlikely to be sustainable as the platform grows. Automated scripts should therefore routinely test whether links to metadata sources, data dictionaries, methodological descriptions, quality statements, and access request pages are still active. Failures should be flagged for review and, where appropriate, communicated to users, because broken documentation pathways impact researchers' ability to assess datasets.

Automation can also support transparency around metadata currency. Scripts should identify records that have exceeded a defined review threshold (for example, no metadata verification within 12 months) or where stated update frequencies are inconsistent with observed changes. By making the presence, absence, and ageing of discovery-relevant metadata measurable, automation helps ensure that the catalogue remains a

trustworthy entry point for social science research, even where underlying administrative data systems remain heterogeneous and unevenly documented.

2.3.3 Monitoring and evaluation

Lastly, the discovery tool should have monitoring and evaluation functions to understand how it is used in practice and ensure that it remains responsive to user needs and can be improved iteratively over time. This includes tracking use through privacy-appropriate measures such as volumes of data access requests (to monitor whether, for example, metadata is sufficiently clear for users to prompt action), filter combinations (to check which filter combinations are central to feasibility assessment and should be prioritised), record views (to monitor which datasets attract most attention), and navigation pathways. Usage data should be complemented by qualitative input from key stakeholder groups, including researchers and other users, data custodians/owners, and technical experts within the product team, to support structured prioritisation of feature improvements and functionality updates over time.

As one suggestion raised during our user consultations, an access-management system such as CADRE (Coordinated Access for Data, Research and Engagement) could potentially be used to track downstream access demand and workflow indicators. CADRE is an access-management platform supported by the Australian Research Data Commons. It is designed to support coordinated, governed access to sensitive data by managing data access requests, approvals, and related workflows in line with the Five Safes framework. CADRE enables tracking of access demand, request status, decision points, and turnaround times across participating custodians, providing visibility into how users move from discovery to formal access processes, rather than functioning as a general-purpose discovery or web analytics tool. For the purposes of this tool it can help with tracking, for example, volumes of data access requests, processing stages, and turnaround times once users move from discovery to request and approval processes. However, we note this as a consultation-informed possibility rather than an adopted design decision at this stage.

2.4 Technical and resource requirements

While Section 2.3 detailed some of the proposed features and functionalities of an interactive metadata catalogue for Australian administrative data assets, this section lays out the technical and resource requirements of building and maintaining such a tool. The construction of the tool has an initial build phase, followed by ongoing maintenance and updating. Each of these phases will require close collaboration between social scientists with expertise in the research uses of the data sources and software developers with the technical expertise to ensure the proper functioning of an interactive, web-based data discovery tool. The discussion of technical and resourcing requirements is informed by initial consultations with members of the TAG referenced in Section 2.2.3, including experts with experience building comparable tool. However, more in-depth consultations will be needed to refine requirements and develop a final tool. Accordingly, the estimates presented in this section should be treated as preliminary.

2.4.1 Planning and build

The initial build phase of the project would be the most intensive technically. It first requires hiring or contracting with a dedicated developer capable of implementing the features and functionalities discussed in Section 2.3. The hiring process would likely favour developers with experience in the platform and hosting technologies chosen. Thus, choices like web hosting (i.e., Nectar versus commercial solutions) might influence hiring or contracting decisions as finding a developer with prior experience would increase efficiency and reduce build times.

Once technical staff are in place, the build phase of the project would proceed with the developer customising an instance of a data management system (e.g., CKAN) to suit the planned needs, features, and functionalities. This phase will require close collaboration between the developer and social scientists

with content expertise to ensure that the specified features and functionalities are implemented and that they operate properly from a researcher's perspective as the end user. Further, a social scientist with expertise in administrative data sources would also work collaboratively with the developer to ensure that back-end data entry interfaces are intuitive, easy to operate, and fit for purpose.

Technical experts we consulted in Section 2.2.3 suggest a single full-stack developer (i.e., a software developer capable of building and maintaining front and back ends) working at full-time would require an estimated six months to complete the build phase of the project. This projected timeline reflects customising an existing data management system (e.g., CKAN) rather than building a completely new one, as some other data discoverability resources have done (e.g., TERN Data Discovery Portal). The developer would be responsible for customising the data management system's back-end data input interface, implementing front-end user experience features, such as custom filters and advanced search capabilities, and customising automated maintenance scripts to check for errors, broken links, when linked web pages have been updated. An advantage of many established data management systems is that such scripts often do not need to be written from scratch, though they may need customization. Further, many metadata fields come as standard inclusions with data management systems, while adding bespoke fields or customising how they are displayed are straightforward, well-tested processes.

In a university context a full-stack developer at the HEW-7 level would likely be sufficient to customize a data management system to adapt content from the Environmental Scan Report. The developer would benefit from, though likely not require, prior experience working with the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud to increase efficiency and reduce time spent learning a new web hosting service, which may be niche relative to larger services offered by Amazon, Google, or Microsoft.

2.4.2 Technical maintenance and running costs

Following the initial build and deployment of an interactive web-based metadata catalogue, such a tool would require ongoing technical maintenance and updating. By technical maintenance and updating (as opposed to content maintenance and updating, which is addressed in Section 2.4.4), we refer to technology-related maintenance and updates required of all websites or data catalogues, including cyber security diligence, patching, and common vulnerabilities and exposures (CVE) mitigation. This includes ensuring that data management platform or other software updates are handled appropriately or that the data catalogues continue to work as designed with updated web browsers across different platforms (e.g., ensuring that browser and operating system updates on desktop computers, tablets, and mobile devices do not cause errors in how pages are displayed). Further, any scripts which run, including those that might interact with external APIs, would be subject to potential errors over time due to updates.

Technical issues in need of attention may be surfaced by scripts which report errors or other means, such as users alerting staff. The sporadic nature of these types of technical issues means that IT support staff must be contracted on an ongoing basis. However, members of the TAG we consulted with suggested that the ongoing maintenance would likely only require roughly 0.1 FTE of a HEW-7 full-stack developer. Any additional content updates or changes to front-end features or back-end functionalities may require additional developer time, and would not be included in the estimate for basic site maintenance.

Another recurring running cost is web hosting services, which have been mentioned previously in this report. Utilising commercial options such as Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud, or Microsoft Azure would be estimated to require \$1,000 (AUD) per year or less. The final costs for ongoing web hosting services would depend on the overall size of the metadata catalogue, its overall number of queries and web traffic, data ingress and egress across zones, and disaster recovery and backups. However, utilising the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud for web hosting services would eliminate these costs, as the Nectar Research Cloud supports Australian university-based research infrastructure tools with free web hosting services.

2.4.3 Contracting

Consultations with TAG members revealed two options for fulfilling the software development staffing requirements: hiring dedicated personnel for an in-house project or contracting with an outside partner such as the Research Computing Centre (RCC) at The University of Queensland or the Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF).

The benefit of hiring dedicated personnel without subcontracting would be the ability to exercise greater control over hiring and ensuring that the developer was dedicated to the specific project. However, there are also several risks inherent in hiring a dedicated developer. For example, properly evaluating a software developer candidates would require a level of technical knowledge that most social scientists lack, likely requiring close collaboration with IT consultants or advisors. Then, even if a well-qualified individual is brought on-board to build and maintain the tool, there are additional practical risks. Because the build phase of the project would likely be six to nine months, it may be difficult to recruit well-qualified candidates. After the initial build phase, transitioning from a full-time (1.0 FTE) role down to part-time (a 0.1 or 0.2 FTE role) would be difficult in practice. If there were other related projects from the same or another funding stream, the developer might transition to focusing on other projects. However, this arrangement would depend on several factors outside the control of the current project. Hiring a single developer rather than subcontracting out also introduces risks of setbacks if the original developer leaves for other employment opportunities. This would cause additional costs to hire a replacement and allow for the new hire to build the understanding of the tool required to properly maintain it.

By contrast, partnering or sub-contracting with the UQ RCC, QCIF, or a similar service provider offers several advantages. First, hiring costs would be limited as a project would fund the time of pre-existing employees. Second, the technical knowledge required to properly evaluate and hire software developers could be outsourced to experts. Third, because these organizations have large teams with staff working across multiple projects, transitioning from requiring a full-time developer for the build to a part-time developer for maintenance would be easier, allowing for a developer to continue devoting part of their time to the discoverability tool while having the remainder of their time being paid for by unrelated projects. Fourth, finding developers with experience using the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud would likely be easier when contracting with organisations that have current or past projects utilising Nectar, including but not limited to the UQ RCC or QCIF. Finally, in the even that a member of the technical staff working on the project leaves, these contracted organisations would be better suited to maintaining continuity by being able to shift staff members rather than hire a completely new developer. However, there are also risks with contracting development out, including the potential for disjointed communication and competing priorities that may be placed on staff contracted to this project.

2.4.4 Content maintenance, updating, and expansion: technical and resource considerations

While the previous sub-section focused on the technical maintenance of an interactive metadata catalogue, there are also resource requirements for the maintenance, updating, and—potentially—expansion of metadata content. Much of this work would need to be overseen by a social scientist with expertise in administrative data sources for research.

Maintaining the content, rather than just the technical aspects of the tool, is important for ensuring that researchers can properly utilise the metadata catalogue for basic data discovery tasks. Since administrative data assets tend to be updated over time, there is a potential for information to become outdated quickly. Additionally, the analysis of broken links (see Section 1.3.1) suggests an annual rate of 14% of links breaking. While some of this may be automated using scripts, finding the corrected links and checking their content may require content expertise (i.e., a social scientist) and some manual rather than purely

automated processes. Thus, monitoring content to maintain the current level of information would require both maintenance work from both the ITC staff and the social science staff.

Additionally, keeping the resource up-to-date will require content updating, distinguished here from 'technical maintenance' because it will require additions and edits to the metadata provided in the catalogue in Attachments 1 and 2. Content updating could arise from two sources: updates to data and updates to metadata. When data are updated to include expanded temporal or geographic scopes, new or expanded populations, or additional variables, metadata reported in the catalogue would need to reflect these changes. Similarly, if variable definitions change or the data otherwise is updated or changed in any way, corresponding metadata must remain up-to-date. While a goal would be to automate as much of this process as possible by, for instance, automatically monitoring source websites for changes, it is likely to still require manual updating by a social science expert to ensure the accuracy of the catalogue. Alternatively, even if there were no or minimal changes to the underlying data, metadata reported by data custodians/owners might be updated. For instance, additional metadata resources, such as variable lists, data dictionaries, or technical or methodological reports, might be released which contain new or updated information which should be relayed to users of the data discovery tool. Again, while automated scripts might surface changes to previously-linked websites, it would likely require some degree of manual checking and updating of records in the back end of the data management system by a social scientist.

In addition to maintaining and updating resources which have already been manually catalogued by the SSRIN, end users may also benefit from expanding the data assets catalogued. With the expansion of administrative data in Australian social science research, there will likely be new data assets which fit the inclusion criteria from Part 1 of this report. Further, state-level data or other data sources not considered as part of the Environmental Scan may also be useful to social science researchers. Expansion of data assets provided in a data catalogue would again require manual collection, organisation, and analysis of publicly-available metadata for new data sources by a social scientist with research experience. The largely manual process of adding data assets to the metadata catalogue would require significant time on the part of social science staff if done at scale. While time spent on each asset can vary according to the complexity and accessibility of data and metadata, adding a new data asset to the catalogue would take roughly two hours for most assets. Furthermore, adding entries also increases the time and resources required for maintaining and updating both the content and technical aspects of the catalogue proportionally.

Thus, in terms of maintenance, updating, and expansion, resource costs for social science staff are likely to exceed those for the purely technical maintenance. The resource requirements may be reduced through building in as much automation as possible, including the potential use of AI tools or agents to check for updated metadata in concert with manual processes. Furthermore, collaboration with data custodians/owners would help to ensure accuracy and potentially surface additional or updated metadata more efficiently.

While the time spent maintaining and updating metadata can be difficult to anticipate, if each of the 97 data assets catalogued in Attachments 1 and 2 were allotted 2 hours annually to be updated by a social science staff member, it would equate to just over 0.1 FTE. This task could likely be completed by a research professional staff member at HEW-7, with oversight from a social science academic. An additional 0.1 FTE for additional, miscellaneous content maintenance and updating (e.g., addressing broken links or other non-regular maintenance tasks) would create a buffer and allow for unanticipated maintenance or improvements to content.

Overall, the scenario laid out above would require a build phase of roughly six months where a full-time (1.0 FTE) HEW-7 developer worked in collaboration with a social science academic and social science research professional staff (HEW-7) at roughly 0.1 FTE each to create a customised CKAN or Dataverse instance to convert the metadata catalogue into an interactive, web-based data discovery tool for Australian

administrative data. The direct costs for personnel for the build phase based on The University of Queensland salary scales would be roughly \$92,000, with indirect on-costs accounting for a further \$46,000. Subsequent maintenance costs at 0.1 FTE for a developer, 0.2 FTE social science research assistant and 0.05 FTE for a social science academic would lead to direct annual costs of roughly \$55,000 with an additional \$28,000 of indirect on-costs.¹⁴

2.5 Conclusion

The development of an interactive, web-based metadata catalogue would have the opportunity to improve the discoverability and understanding of Australian administrative data for social scientific research purposes. Currently, Australian administrative data assets are inconsistently documented and publicised. This poses a barrier for social science, where social scientists are often unaware of potentially useful data assets or unable to assess the potential usefulness of data assets at the early stages of the research journey. Thus, the potential of existing administrative data assets goes unmet due to a lack of intuitively organised, informative, and well-publicised metadata. A metadata catalogue built with the information that users, i.e., social science researchers, need most has the potential to substantially reduce these obstacles and unlock the power of administrative data.

Following the environmental scan of administrative data assets, we reviewed existing data discoverability tools and catalogues and consulted with social science researchers and with technical experts. The consultations and review of existing discoverability tools revealed the desire for an interactive metadata catalogue focused on informing researchers about potential uses of sensitive, unit-record administrative data assets. Given access restrictions of such data assets, a data discoverability tool would only include metadata unlike many existing tools which provide access to publicly available data, such as AURIN's provision of aggregate geo-coded datasets. Consultations with technical experts suggested the use of open-source data management systems which combine back-end and front-end capabilities to catalogue, organise, and display metadata to users. The most popular open-source options, such as CKAN and Dataverse, have well-supported features, large user communities, including the Australian government (CKAN) and Australian Data Archive (Dataverse), reducing risks related to ongoing support while also keeping infrastructure costs low. Further, utilising web the ARDC Nectar Cloud for web-hosting services would help keep technical maintenance costs to a minimum.

Part 2 of this report also revealed ongoing technical and substantive challenges. Technical challenges include routine platform maintenance and site reliability engineering, which are often underestimated. Updates to data management systems, web browsers, hosting services, and other services or software that interact with the discoverability tool can cause errors or outages. Links to sources of metadata, such as data custodian/owner information pages, can also update or change without notice, meaning that information can become outdated or unusable without regular maintenance, including automatically checking for broken links. Other substantive maintenance challenges include keeping abreast of content changes in metadata and in changes to the underlying data collections. Further, because assets included in the Environmental Scan focus are updated regularly, many metadata fields such as temporal coverage would need to be updated on a regular basis to maintain accuracy. As such, the long-term utility of a discoverability tool would rely on infrastructure, staffing, processes, and partnerships with data custodians/owners to maintain its technical capabilities and informational accuracy and completeness.

¹⁴ Costs for the build phase assume a full-time HEW-7 (step 4) developer for six months, plus six months of a HEW-7 (step 4) research assistant at 0.2 FTE and a Level C (step 6) academic at 0.05 FTE with 50% indirect costs. Costs for ongoing annual maintenance assume a HEW-7 (step 4) developer at 0.1 FTE, a HEW-7 (step 4) research assistant at 0.2 FTE, and a Level C (step 6) academic at 0.05 FTE with 50% indirect. All staff were costed at the highest step within their respective levels

A well-designed, research user-centred metadata catalogue for administrative data assets would offer value to social scientists by consolidating fragmented metadata sources and providing consistent, actionable information that researchers need, including information about the scope and coverage, topical content, units of observation, and access conditions. This would allow Australian social scientists to harness the full power of administrative data sources by increasing the efficiency of researchers already working with administrative data and by making these powerful data assets more accessible to new researchers or those without previous administrative data experience, thereby expanding the field of researchers working with administrative data assets. By increasing both the number of researchers and their efficiency, a dedicated data discoverability tool and metadata catalogue can help Australian social scientists to uncover the evidence needed to shape emerging and enduring challenges for Australian society.

Glossary of Acronyms

ABS	Australian Bureau of Statistics
AIFS	Australian Institute of Family Studies
AIHW	Australian Institute of Health and Welfare
ALife	ATO Longitudinal Files
AMEP	Australian Migrant English Program
ATO	Australian Taxation Office
BEBOLD	Better Evidence Better Outcomes Linked Data
BLADE	Business Longitudinal Data Analysis Environment
CheReL	Centre for Health Record Linkage
DHAC	Department of Health and Aged Care
DOMINO	Data Over Multiple Individual Occurrences
DSS	Department of Social Services
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
HASS+I ARDC	Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences and Indigenous Australian Research Data Commons
HILDA	Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia
JJ NMDS	Juvenile Justice National Minimum Data Set
LCDI	Life Course Data Initiative
LSIC	Longitudinal Study of Indigenous Children
MADIP	Multi-Agency Data Integration Project
METEOR	Metadata Online Registry
NDDA	National Disability Data Asset
NDIA	National Disability Insurance Agency
NMDS	National Minimum Data Set
PHRN	Public Health Research Network
PLIDA	Person Level Integrated Data Asset
SSRIN	Social Science Research Infrastructure Network
YJ NMDS	Youth Justice National Minimum Data Set

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Appendix A - Comparison of CKAN and Dataverse features

Table 11. Comparison of CKAN and Dataverse features relevant to the proposed data infrastructure platform (adapted from Boch et al. (2022))

Feature	CKAN	Dataverse
Version	2.9	5.6
Installation wizard	No	Yes
Installable from repository	Yes	Yes
Distributed as container image	Yes	Yes
Licence	AGPL	Apache
Ecosystem of extensions	Yes	Yes
Internationalisation support	Yes	Yes
Multi-factor authentication	Yes	No
Authorisation (access control)	Yes	Yes
Federated identity / Single sign-on	Plugin	Yes
Review system	No	No
Maturity	Yes	Yes
Programming language	Python	Java
Billing / payment system	No	No
Documentation	Yes	Yes
Cloud storage interface	Plugin	Yes
Exporting schemas	No	Yes
Dataset versioning	Plugin	Yes
Dataset licence specification	Yes	Yes
Faceted search	Yes	Yes
Duplicate detection	No	No
Established ontologies	Plugin	Yes
Customised ontologies	Partially	No
Domain-specific vocabularies	Yes	Plugin
Customised vocabularies	Partially	Plugin
Data provenance management	Plugin	No
Diverse data types	Yes	Yes
Exporting and RDF serialisation	Yes	Plugin
Harvesting / crawling of datasets	Yes	Yes
Batch access API	Plugin	Yes
Transactional access API	Yes	Yes
Analytical access API	Plugin	Plugin
Data visualisation	Yes	Yes
SWORD compliance	No	Yes
Data anonymisation	No	No

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Australian Research Data Commons

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NCRIS
National Research Infrastructure for Australia
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